

Master Thesis

A Low-Rank Parareal Solver for Differential Riccati Equations Written in Julia

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Glossary

Abbreviations

ADI alternating-directions implicit. 1, 8, 9, 15, 21, 23–28, 30, 31, 33, 41, 43, 57, 59, 67–69

ALE algebraic Lyapunov equation. 1, 8, 14, 15, 21, 25, 26, 28, 30, 33, 41, 43, 59, 67–69, 71

AOT ahead-of-time. 47, 50

ARE algebraic Riccati equation. 7, 8, 11

DRE differential Riccati equation. 1, 2, 4–8, 10, 11, 13–16, 18, 19, 41, 43, 57, 67

HJE Hamilton-Jacobi equation. 3, 5

IO input/output, usually from/to permanent storage or over the network. 51

IVP initial value problem. 13, 35, 38, 39, 45, 50

JIT just-in-time. 47, 49–51, 67

LQR linear quadratic regulator. 4, 6, 7

LRCF low-rank Cholesky-type factorization. 11, 16, 59

LRSIF low-rank symmetric indefinite factorization. 12, 15, 16, 18, 21, 26, 31, 35, 40–43, 52, 53, 57, 59, 60, 62, 67, 68

LTI linear time-invariant. 4, 6

LTV linear time-varying. 4

OCP optimal control problem. 3, 7, 57

ODE ordinary differential equation. 1, 4, 5, 13, 35, 45, 46

PDE partial differential equation. 1, 9, 21

Numbers and Vector Spaces

\mathbb{N}	set of natural numbers.
\mathbb{R}	field of real numbers.
\mathbb{C}	field of complex numbers.
\mathbb{C}_-	left complex half plane, $\mathbb{C}_- := \{z \in \mathbb{C} : \operatorname{Re}(z) < 0\}$.
\mathbb{K}^n	vector space of n -tuples having entries in \mathbb{K} .
$\mathbb{K}^{m \times n}$	vector space of $m \times n$ matrices having entries in \mathbb{K} .
i	imaginary unit, $i^2 = -1$.
$\overline{(\cdot)}$	complex conjugate of a scalar or matrix, $\overline{a + bi} := a - bi$ for $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$.
$\operatorname{Re}(\cdot) / \operatorname{Im}(\cdot)$	real/imaginary part of a scalar or matrix, $\operatorname{Re}(a + bi) := a$, $\operatorname{Im}(a + bi) := b$ for $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$.

Norms

$ \cdot $	absolute value of a scalar.
$\ \cdot\ _2$	Euclidean norm of a vector, $\ x\ _2 := \sqrt{x^H x}$ for $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, or spectral norm of a matrix, $\ A\ _2 := \max_{\ x\ _2=1} \ Ax\ _2 = \rho(A)$.
$\ \cdot\ _F$	Frobenius norm of a vector or matrix, $\ X\ _F^2 := \sum_{i,j} x_{ij} ^2$.

Matrices

I_n	identity matrix of size $n \in \mathbb{N}$.
$(\cdot)^T / (\cdot)^H$	transpose / Hermitian transpose of a matrix.
$(\cdot)^{-T} / (\cdot)^{-H}$	inverse of the transpose / Hermitian transpose of a (square) matrix.
$(\cdot)^{-1}$	inverse of a (square) matrix.
$(\cdot)^\dagger$	Moore-Penrose pseudo inverse of a matrix.
$\operatorname{rank}(\cdot)$	rank of a matrix.
$\operatorname{span}(\cdot)$	vector space spanned by the columns of a matrix.
$\Lambda(\cdot) / \Lambda(\cdot, \cdot)$	spectrum of a matrix / matrix pair, $\Lambda(A) := \Lambda(A, I)$, $\Lambda(A, E) := \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \exists v : Av = \lambda Ev\}$.
$\rho(\cdot)$	spectral radius of a matrix, $\rho(G) := \max\{ \lambda : \lambda \in \Lambda(G)\}$.
$\operatorname{nnz}(\cdot)$	number of non-zero entries of a matrix.

Relations

$X \geq 0 / Y > 0$	positive semi-definite matrix X / positive definite matrix Y , $\Lambda(X) \subseteq \{\lambda \in \mathbb{R} : \lambda \geq 0\}$, $\Lambda(Y) \subseteq \{\lambda \in \mathbb{R} : \lambda > 0\}$.
$f(x) \stackrel{!}{\Delta} 0$	determine x such that $f(x) \Delta 0$ holds, where $\Delta \in \{=, >\}$ is a relation.
\ll	much less than.
\equiv	pointwise equality of functions.
\cong	equality up to an isomorphism.

Derivatives

$f'(x) := \frac{df}{dx}(x)$	first derivative of f .
$\dot{x} := \frac{dx}{dt}$	derivative of x w.r.t. time t .
$V_z := \frac{\partial V}{\partial z}$	partial derivative of V w.r.t. z .
$V_z(t, z) _{z=x}$	partial derivative of V w.r.t. z , evaluated at $(t, z) = (t, x)$.

Variables and Constants

k	ADI or parareal step.
k_n	last parareal refinement $U_n^{k_n}$ computed by stage n .
K	depending on the context: feedback matrix $K(t) := R^{-1}B^T X(t)E \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, or maximum number of parareal steps/refinements allowed, $k \leq K$.
m	number of system controls $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $m \ll n$.
n	depending on the context: number of system states $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, or specific time step t_n , $1 \leq n \leq N$.
N	number of time steps $t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_N = t_f$.
q	number of system outputs $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$, $q \ll n$.
t_0 and t_f	initial and final time, $t_0 < t_f$.
$t_F = t_F(n, k)$	runtime of fine solver $F(U_{n-1}^k)$.
$t_G = t_G(n, k)$	runtime of coarse solver $G(U_{n-1}^k)$.
\hat{t}_*	estimate of t_* .
u_{mach}	machine precision.

Introduction

Current challenges in science and engineering require a fast iteration on (intermediate) ideas and designs, which in turn demands highly performant algorithms. In this context, efficiency may only be a secondary concern. Meanwhile, modern computer architectures are dominated by parallelism: multiple cores per CPU, multiple CPUs per node, and multiple nodes per cluster. Many real-world application can be modeled by partial differential equations (PDEs) or ordinary differential equations (ODEs), which describe the behavior of an underlying system in space and time. A common strategy is to solve these equations *parallel-in-space*, i.e. to distribute the spatial domain onto several CPUs, which are then usually worked on in lockstep along the time dimension. This strategy only scales as far as the local problems do not become too small, due to the communication necessary along the interfaces of spatial sub-domains. Another strategy is to (also) solve the problem *parallel-in-time*, i.e. to distribute the temporal domain onto several CPUs. An algorithm of the latter strategy is the so-called parareal method [18], which is the focus of this thesis. From an energy efficiency perspective, the parareal method is not worth pursuing. However, as engineering demands fast cycle times, this method can lead to large speed-ups.

In this thesis, the parareal method shall be applied to the matrix-valued differential Riccati equation (DRE), which arises e.g. in optimal control and model order reduction. Discretizations of real-world problems quickly lead to large-scale systems, for which the solution matrices easily reach thousands of rows and columns. In order to handle them efficiently, one uses the problem's inherent rapid decay of singular values to approximate the solution matrices in a low-rank factorization, see e.g. [14, 15, 25]. This low-rank approach sets this thesis apart from the work of Köhler, Lang, and Saak [13], who use a dense parareal scheme. As the rank of the solution approximation varies in time, an implementation using well-established frameworks like OpenMPI¹ would be more involved. Since Julia [6] promises to provide a fresh perspective on high-performance computing problems, this thesis serves as a test project for just that.

The thesis is structured as follows. Chapter 2 gives an overview of the DRE arising in optimal control of a linear dynamical system, and Chapter 3 presents the general techniques used to handle large-scale problems. Then, Chapter 4 shows how to adapt a first-order and a second-order Rosenbrock method to the matrix-valued DRE. Every step of the Rosenbrock method requires the solution of an algebraic Lyapunov equation (ALE), which may be done using e.g. the alternating-directions implicit (ADI) method described

¹<https://www.open-mpi.org/>

in Chapter 5. This completes the general building blocks of a DRE solver. To improve the performance of the solver, Chapter 6 shows how to apply the parareal method to the particular low-rank factorization used in this thesis. Chapter 7 describes the implementation of the aforementioned algorithms in the form of two Julia packages, which have been created for this thesis. The chapter also presents the numerical results of applying these packages to a small configuration of the Rail benchmark problem [22], which goes back to Benner and Saak [5]. The chapter compares low-rank and dense algorithms in sequential and parareal execution. Finally, Chapter 8 briefly summarizes the findings and future research or optimization opportunities.

Hardware and Software Used

The numerical experiments throughout this thesis were performed on up to 29 standard nodes (450 cores) of the Linux cluster Mechthild² at the Max Planck Institute for Dynamics of Complex Technical Systems in Magdeburg, each having two Intel Xeon Skylake Silver 4110 with 8 cores per CPU and 192 GB of memory, or on a laptop (MacBook Pro, 13-inch, 2018, macOS 11) having an Intel Core i5-8259U with 4 cores and 16 GB of memory. Each process uses a single Julia thread and, unless stated otherwise, one BLAS³/LAPACK⁴ thread.

DrWatson.jl [8] was used to assist data management. The dense DRE solvers are built on top of MatrixEquations.jl [30]. DifferentialEquations.jl [26] was used for Example 6.2. The figures in this thesis were created with Makie.jl [7] or TikZ [29]. Julia was used in version 1.6.1 on Mechthild and 1.6.2 on the laptop.

Code Availability

The \LaTeX and Julia source codes for this thesis may be found at:

```
https://github.com/jonas-schulze/master-thesis
https://github.com/mpimd-csc/DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl
https://github.com/mpimd-csc/ParaReal.jl
```

Additionally, this document as well as the slides used during the defense, and some of the log files may be found at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7843198>

The present version of the document corresponds to git hash 6711f9b.

²<https://www.mpi-magdeburg.mpg.de/cluster/mechthild>

³<http://www.netlib.org/blas/>

⁴<http://www.netlib.org/lapack/>

Hamilton-Jacobi Theory

This chapter gives an overview of the Riccati equations arising in the optimal control of a linear dynamical system following Locatelli [19], as well as the Lyapunov equation to be seen in this thesis. For a more general overview of matrix equations refer to e.g. Simoncini [27].

2.1 Finite Control Horizon

Consider the optimal control problem (OCP)

$$\begin{aligned} \min_u \quad & \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \ell(t, x(t), u(t)) dt + m(t_f, x(t_f)) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \dot{x} = f(t, x, u), \quad x(t_0) = x_0 \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

using *state* $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, system *input* or *control* $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and scalar cost functions ℓ and m . Following [19], a sufficient condition for an optimal control u^* solving problem (2.1) may be stated by means of a continuously differentiable *value function* $V : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying the Hamilton-Jacobi equation (HJE)

$$V_t(t, z) + H(t, z, u^h, V_z(t, z)^T) = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

for any $z \in \mathbb{R}^n$, as well as

$$V(t_f, z) = m(t_f, z) \quad (2.3)$$

for all admissible final events (t_f, z) . V_t and V_z denote the partial derivatives of V , the *Hamiltonian* $H : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is given by

$$H(t, z, u, \lambda) := \ell(t, z, u) + \lambda^T f(t, z, u) \quad (2.4)$$

and $u^h := u^h(t, z, V_z(t, z)^T)$ denotes the H -minimizing control.⁵ Namely, a control u^* is optimal if it fulfills the feedback law

$$u^*(t) = u^h(t, x(t), V_z(t, z)^T|_{z=x(t)}), \quad (2.5)$$

where x is determined by $\dot{x} = f(t, x, u^*)$ and $x(t_0) = x_0$, cf. [19, Corollary 2.1].

⁵It is $H(t, z, u^h, \lambda) < H(t, z, u, \lambda)$ for $u \neq u^h = u^h(t, z, \lambda)$. H is said to be *regular* if u^h exists and is unique for any t, z, λ . Here, this is always assumed to be the case.

In the remainder of this section, this theory is applied to the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) tracking problem consisting of a linear ODE and quadratic cost functions, which aim to steer a system close to a desired trajectory. Only a very brief outline of the ideas leading to a DRE is given here, following [19, Remarks 3.3 and 3.6] and [15, Section 3.2.2], to which the reader may refer to for further details.

Many applications can be expressed by means of a linear (*standard*) *state-space system*

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = Ax + Bu \\ y = Cx \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

consisting of, again, *state* $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and *input* or *control* $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$. The system's *output* is denoted with $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$, where $q \ll n$, as for most applications it is impossible to measure the whole state x . The dynamics of the system are described by the *state-space matrix* $A(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, *input map* $B(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, and *output map* $C(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times n}$. Further, let the cost functions be given by the squared weighted norms

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(t, x, u) &= \frac{1}{2} \|y - \hat{y}\|_Q^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|u\|_R^2 \\ m(t, x) &= \frac{1}{2} \|y - \hat{y}\|_S^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

for symmetric positive-definite weight matrices $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times q}$, $R \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, and $S \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times q}$. The variable $\hat{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$ describes a desired trajectory the modeled system should follow, e.g. by measurements of a real system, or economic requirements of the technical process behind it. The system (2.6) is called linear time-invariant (LTI) if the *system matrices* $A(t), B(t), C(t)$ are constant for $t \in [t_0, t_f]$, and linear time-varying (LTV) otherwise. This thesis only considers LTI and *controllable* systems, i.e. for any given (t_0, x_0) and (t_1, x_1) , $t_1 > t_0$, there exists a bounded control $u(\cdot)$ such that $x(t_1; t_0, x_0, u(\cdot)) = x_1$.

The Hamiltonian (2.4) is then given by

$$H(t, z, u, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2} \|Cz - \hat{y}\|_Q^2 + \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\|u\|_R^2}_{u^T R u} + \lambda^T (Az + Bu),$$

causing the H -minimizing control u^h to be defined by

$$H_u = Ru^h + B^T \lambda \stackrel{!}{=} 0, \quad H_{uu} = R \stackrel{!}{>} 0.$$

The second order criterion is fulfilled by construction, and ensures the existence of R^{-1} . Thus, the first order criterion implies

$$u^h(t, z, \lambda) = -R^{-1} B^T \lambda. \quad (2.8)$$

Making the ansatz

$$V(t, z) := \frac{1}{2} z^T X(t) z + w(t)^T z + v(t) \quad (2.9)$$

for the value function, its partial derivatives read

$$\begin{aligned} V_t &= \frac{1}{2}z^T \dot{X}z + \dot{w}^T z + \dot{v} \\ V_z &= z^T X + w^T. \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

Substituting the above, $u^h(t, z, V_z^T)$ based on Equation (2.8), as well as the scalar identity

$$z^T X A z = \frac{1}{2} \left(z^T X A z + (z^T X A z)^T \right) \quad (2.11)$$

into the HJE (2.2), and regrouping based on the order of z yields

$$0 = \frac{1}{2}z^T (\dot{X} + C^T Q C + X A + A^T X^T - X B R^{-1} B^T X^T) z \quad (2.12a)$$

$$+ (\dot{w}^T + w^T A - w^T B R^{-1} B^T X^T - \hat{y}^T Q C) z \quad (2.12b)$$

$$+ \left(\dot{v} - \frac{1}{2} (w^T B R^{-1} B^T w - \hat{y} Q \hat{y}) \right), \quad (2.12c)$$

while the final condition (2.3) reads

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{2}z(t_f)^T X(t_f)z(t_f) + w^T(t_f)z(t_f) + v(t_f) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}z(t_f)^T (C^T S C)z(t_f) - (\hat{y}(t_f)^T S C)z(t_f) + \left(\frac{1}{2}\hat{y}(t_f)^T S \hat{y}(t_f)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

Sufficient conditions are obtained by letting Equation (2.12) be the (multivariate) zero polynomial in z , and by comparing the coefficients of the terms in z in Equation (2.13). Upon noting that if X fulfills the dynamics of (2.12a), so does X^T , this leads to a DRE in $X(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$,

$$\begin{cases} \dot{X} = -(C^T Q C + X A + A^T X - X B R^{-1} B^T X) \\ X(t_f) = C^T S C, \end{cases} \quad (2.14)$$

an ODE in $w(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the so-called *adjoint state equation*,

$$\begin{cases} \dot{w} = -(A^T - X B R^{-1} B^T)w + C^T Q \hat{y} \\ w(t_f) = -C^T S \hat{y}(t_f), \end{cases} \quad (2.15)$$

and another ODE in $v(t) \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\begin{cases} \dot{v} = \frac{1}{2} (w^T B R^{-1} B^T w - \hat{y} Q \hat{y}) \\ v(t_f) = \frac{1}{2} \hat{y}(t_f)^T S \hat{y}(t_f), \end{cases} \quad (2.16)$$

all to be solved backwards in time, $t \in [t_0, t_f]$.

However, the optimal control u^* given by the feedback law (2.5),

$$\begin{aligned} u^*(t) &= -R^{-1} B^T V_z(t, x(t))^T \\ &= -R^{-1} B^T \underbrace{(X(t) x(t) + w(t))}_{=: K(t)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

does not require v . The overall cost to compute u^* is dominated by solving the DRE (2.14). Furthermore, the full solution $X(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is not needed. Rather, it suffices to store the so-called *gain- or feedback matrix* $K(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$. Since typically $m \ll n$, this has a major impact on the storage requirements.

Remark. A *generalized* linear state-space system

$$\begin{cases} E\dot{x} = Ax + Bu \\ y = Cx \end{cases} \quad (2.18)$$

with invertible *mass matrix* $E(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is equivalent to the standard state-space system

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\tilde{x}} = \tilde{A}\tilde{x} + Bu \\ y = \tilde{C}\tilde{x} \end{cases} \quad (2.19)$$

where $\tilde{x} := Ex$, $\tilde{A} := AE^{-1}$ and $\tilde{C} := CE^{-1}$. By applying the theory above and avoiding the inversion of E in the resulting equations, one obtains the generalized DRE

$$\begin{cases} E^T \dot{X}E = -(C^T QC + E^T XA + A^T XE - E^T XBR^{-1}B^T XE) \\ E^T X(t_f)E = C^T SC, \end{cases} \quad (2.20)$$

and the generalized adjoint state equation

$$\begin{cases} E^T \dot{w} = -(A^T - E^T XBR^{-1}B^T)w + C^T Q\hat{y} \\ E^T w(t_f) = -C^T S\hat{y}(t_f). \end{cases} \quad (2.21)$$

The feedback matrix K is then given by

$$K(t) = R^{-1}B^T X(t)E. \quad (2.22)$$

△

Example 2.1 (Parameters of Rail Problem). The Rail benchmark problem [22] is a generalized state-space system that has $m = 7$ controls and $q = 6$ outputs. The variant used in this thesis has $n = 371$ state variables. Furthermore, the LQR weights are

$$Q = I_q, \quad R = I_m, \quad S = \frac{1}{100}I_q,$$

such that $K(t) = B^T X(t)E$ and $E^T X(t_f)E = C^T C/100$. The problem's time span $[0, 4500]$ corresponds to a resolution of 10 ms, i.e. $t_f = 45$ s. △

Only the LTI case with invertible E is covered in this thesis. In fact, most computations will be performed for the problem above. Therefore, Q and R are assumed to be identity matrices of appropriate size.

2.2 Infinite Control Horizon

Consider the OCP for a LQR over an infinite time horizon,

$$\begin{aligned} \min_u \quad & \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \ell(t, x(t), u(t)) dt \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \dot{x} = Ax + Bu, \quad x(t_0) = x_0. \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

For $\ell(t, x, u) = \frac{1}{2} \|Cx - \hat{y}(t)\|_Q^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|u\|_R^2$ as in Equation (2.7), following the proof of Lo-catelli [19, Theorem 3.2], the optimal control is given by

$$u^*(t) = -R^{-1}B^T(\bar{X}(t)x(t) + \bar{w}(t)) \quad (2.24)$$

for some $\bar{w}(t)$, where $\bar{X}(t) := \lim_{t_f \rightarrow \infty} X(t; t_f)$ and $X(\cdot; t_f)$ is a solution to the DRE (2.14) having homogeneous boundary data $X(t_f; t_f) = 0$. By [19, Theorem 3.3], $\bar{X}(t) \equiv \bar{X}$ is constant. Hence, its derivative is zero such that \bar{X} is a solution to the algebraic Riccati equation (ARE)

$$C^TQC + \bar{X}A + A^T\bar{X} - \bar{X}BR^{-1}B^T\bar{X} = 0. \quad (2.25)$$

Compare this to the feedback law (2.17) for a finite time horizon, where $X(t)$ is time-dependent. To summarize:

Theorem 2.2 (LQR over Infinite Time Horizon). The solution $X(\cdot)$ to the DRE (2.14) converges at any fixed $t < t_f$ to a solution \bar{X} of the ARE (2.25) for $t_f \rightarrow \infty$. \triangle

Proof. Let $X_f := C^TSC$. The translation $Y(t) := X(t) - X_f$ leads to a DRE in Y having homogeneous boundary data $Y(t_f) = 0$. Then, by [19, Theorem 3.3] for any fixed $t < t_f$ and $t_f \rightarrow \infty$, $Y(\cdot)$ converges to a solution \bar{Y} of its corresponding ARE. Therefore, $X(t) = Y(t) + X_f$ converges to $\bar{X} := \bar{Y} + X_f$, which happens to be a solution to the ARE (2.25). \square

2.3 Forward in Time Formulation

As mentioned previously, the DRE (2.14) has to be solved backwards in time. It is common practice to formulate it forward in time instead by defining

$$\tilde{X}(t) := X(t_f - t + t_0) \quad (2.26)$$

such that

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\tilde{X}}(t) &= -\dot{X}(t_f - t + t_0) = +(C^TQC + A^T\tilde{X}(t) + \tilde{X}(t)A - \tilde{X}(t)BR^{-1}B^T\tilde{X}(t)) \\ \tilde{X}(t_0) &= X(t_f - t_0 + t_0) = X(t_f) = C^TSC \end{aligned} \quad (2.27)$$

and still $t \in [t_0, t_f]$. Overall, the DRE formulated forwards in time reads

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\tilde{X}} = C^TQC + A^T\tilde{X} + \tilde{X}A - \tilde{X}BR^{-1}B^T\tilde{X} \\ \tilde{X}(t_0) = C^TSC. \end{cases} \quad (2.28)$$

As both variants of the DRE, (2.14) and (2.28), may easily be transformed into one another, the notation A, B, C, X is used for both in this thesis.

2.4 Solution of the Differential Riccati Equation

The application of any implicit time-stepping method applied to a generalized DRE

$$E^T \dot{X}E = C^T C + A^T XE + E^T XA - E^T XBB^T XE \quad (2.29)$$

will yield some generalized ARE

$$A^T XE + E^T XA - E^T XSXE = -W, \quad W = W^T, \quad S = S^T \quad (2.30)$$

to be solved at every step [9], as cited in [16, p. 50]. Some methods, including the Rosenbrock-type methods to be covered in Chapter 4, only require a generalized ALE

$$A^T XE + E^T XA = -W, \quad W = W^T \quad (2.31)$$

to be solved at every step, which is a special case of the ARE. ALEs may be solved e.g. using the ADI method, which will be covered in Chapter 5.

Remark. Equations (2.30) and (2.31) are often referred to as continuous-time ARE and ALE, cf. [15, Remark 2.11]. \triangle

Remark. The matrices denoted with A and W in Equations (2.29), (2.30), and (2.31) are not necessarily the same. Matrix S in Equation (2.30) is not related to the weight matrix of Section 2.1. \triangle

Theorem 2.3 (Solvability of DRE). Let $X_0 \geq 0$. Then there exists a unique solution X of the generalized DRE (2.29) with initial condition $E^T X(t_0)E = X_0$ for $t \geq t_0$. Furthermore, $X(\cdot) \geq 0$. \triangle

Proof. Compare [15, Theorem 2.7], [1, Theorem 4.1.6] for $W = C^T C \geq 0$, $S = BB^T \geq 0$. \square

Theorem 2.4 (Solvability of ALE). Let $\lambda_j \neq -\lambda_k$ for any $\lambda_j, \lambda_k \in \Lambda(A, E)$. Then there exists a unique solution X of the generalized ALE (2.31). \triangle

Proof. Compare [15, Theorem 2.10], [1, Corollary 1.1.4]. \square

Example 2.5 (Regularity of Rail Problem). For the Rail benchmark [22], it holds $E > 0$ and $A < 0$, i.e. the system is *stable*. As $E^T X_0 E = C^T C / 100 \geq 0$, the associated generalized DRE has a unique solution. \triangle

Large-Scale Matrix Equations

This chapter will give a very brief overview of common strategies necessary to solve large-scale matrix equations. First, Section 3.1 is concerned with suitable representations of matrices having only very few non-zero entries. Section 3.2 then shows an efficient strategy to solve shifted linear systems. Finally, Section 3.3 presents memory-efficient representations of matrices having a low (numerical) rank.

3.1 Sparse Matrices

Many matrices arising in practical applications are sparse. For example, the shape regularity of the space triangulation of a PDE implies that each node has about the same number of neighbors, and that number mainly depends on the space dimension of the problem. For the matrix corresponding to that triangulation, this number of neighbors determines the number of non-zero entries in the column or row corresponding to that particular node.

Example 3.1 (Sparsity of Rail Problem). The system matrices of the Rail benchmark [22] of size $n = 371$ are sparse. Their patterns are shown in Figure 3.1, as well as the number of non-zero entries $\text{nnz}(\cdot)$ per matrix. E has 4 to 11 entries per row, A has 3 to 11, both have about 6.3 entries per row on average. For a uniform mesh of equilaterals covering \mathbb{R}^2 that number would be 6. △

The common idea to represent a sparse matrix in memory is to only store the non-zero entries, as well as their location within the matrix. Perhaps the most common implementation is the so-called Compressed Column Storage (CCS), sometimes called Compressed Sparse Column (CSC) format. It's the format that e.g. MATLAB⁶ and Julia⁷ use by default.

3.2 Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury Formula

Anticipating the coming chapters, the ADI method has to solve a number of linear systems of the form

$$(A + \alpha^{-1}UV)X = B, \tag{3.1}$$

⁶https://www.mathworks.com/help/pdf_doc/otherdocs/simax.pdf

⁷<https://docs.julialang.org/en/v1.6/stdlib/SparseArrays/>

Figure 3.1: Sparsity pattern of A , B (right), and C (bottom) of Rail problem for $n = 371$, as well as their number of non-zero entries $\text{nnz}(\cdot)$. The pattern of E looks very similar to the one of A , only having 2 entries more.

where the system matrix has the structure of a low-rank update. $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is usually sparse, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ is a scalar, and $U, V^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times k}$ are dense and have a low rank $k \ll n$. Therefore, the product $UV \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is dense, which makes assembling the system matrix infeasible for many applications. Still, the solution X to that updated system is itself a rank- k update of the solution to the non-updated system $AX = B$, see e.g. [11, 28]. This is summarized by the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula:

$$(A + \alpha^{-1}UV)^{-1} = A^{-1} - A^{-1}U(\alpha I_k + VA^{-1}U)^{-1}VA^{-1} \quad (3.2)$$

That is, instead of performing a dense solve w.r.t. $A + \alpha^{-1}UV \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, one only has to solve systems involving the sparse $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ as well as the dense but much smaller $\alpha I_k + VA^{-1}U \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$.

3.3 Low-Rank Representations

Even for sparse system matrices E, A, B, C the solution X of a DRE is in general dense. However, it usually is of low numerical rank, cf. e.g. Penzl [25], Lang [15, Section 2.1.4], and Kürschner [14, Sections 2.3.3 and 2.3.4] and the references therein. The extent of this phenomenon is motivated by the following example.

Example 3.2 (Low-Rank Solution of Rail Problem). The solution of the Rail benchmark [22] is given by the generalized DRE (2.29),

$$\begin{cases} E^T \dot{X}E = C^T C + A^T XE + E^T XA - E^T XBB^T XE \\ E^T X(t_0)E = \frac{1}{100} C^T C. \end{cases}$$

Following Theorem 2.2, $X(t)$ converges to \bar{X} as $t \rightarrow \infty$, where \bar{X} is a solution of the generalized ARE

$$0 = C^T C + A^T \bar{X}E + E^T \bar{X}A - E^T \bar{X}BB^T \bar{X}E.$$

That is, on one end of the time span it holds $\text{rank} X(t_0) = \text{rank} C = q = 6$, while past the other end X converges to a matrix having $\text{rank} \bar{X} \approx 113$. As the corresponding optimal control has some form of minimal energy, one can expect the numerical rank of the solution $X(\cdot)$ to depend on the ranks of its initial and limit value, and to be not much larger in between. For this particular example that's about $\frac{1}{3}n$, which means that the storage requirement of a single matrix can ideally be reduced by about $\frac{2}{3}$. \triangle

Classical Formulation As $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is symmetric and positive semi-definite, the classical approach would be a low-rank Cholesky-type factorization (LRCF) $X = ZZ^T$ for $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$, $r \ll n$. The idea is then to only compute the low-rank factor Z and never evaluate the full X . This requires low-rank formulations for addition and subtraction of low-rank matrices. Let AA^T and $BB^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ be defined. While an update for the LRCF is straight-forward,

$$AA^T + BB^T = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A^T \\ B^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.3)$$

a downdate is more involved. One option is to use complex arithmetic, i.e.

$$AA^T - BB^T = \begin{bmatrix} A & iB \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A^T \\ iB^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.4)$$

where $i^2 = -1$. This has several drawbacks, though. The mathematical one is that the solution to the DRE is expected to be real. Hence, the imaginary part should converge to zero quickly, or there should be an equivalent real-valued factorization. This leads to the technical drawback of a $2\times$ overhead of complex arithmetic over real arithmetic.

Another option is therefore to handle the parts separately which are added versus subtracted in the superposition. The actual difference is then only computed at the very end. While this may only require updates, the overall result suffers from numerical cancellation [16, p. 50] [15, p. 186, thesis 10].

Algorithm 3.1: Column Compression for LRSIFs

Input: $G \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times k}$, $S \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$

Output: $G_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$, $S_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ such that $G_r S_r G_r^T \approx G S G^T$ and $r \leq k$

- 1 Compute $G = QR\Pi^T$ with $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times k}$, $R \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$ and a permutation $\Pi \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$
- 2 Compute a decomposition $R\Pi^T S \Pi R^T = V\Lambda V^T$ with $V \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$ and a diagonal matrix $\Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$ with diagonal entries $|\lambda_1| \geq \dots \geq |\lambda_k|$
Let u_{mach} denote the machine precision.
- 3 $\varepsilon \leftarrow k u_{\text{mach}}$
- 4 Select $r \leq k$ such that $|\lambda_r| \geq \varepsilon \max\{1, \lambda_1\} \geq |\lambda_{r+1}|$
Let V_r denote the first r columns of V and Λ_r the first diagonal block of Λ .
- 5 $G_r \leftarrow QV_r$
- 6 $S_r \leftarrow \Lambda_r$

Indefinite Formulation A different strategy to represent matrices of low numerical rank is the low-rank symmetric indefinite factorization (LRSIF) $X = LDL^T$ for $L \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ and $D \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, $D = D^T$, $r \ll n$. It first appeared in the work of Benner, Li, and Truhar [4]. This factorization does not require up- and downdate to be handled separately,

$$ACA^T \pm BDB^T = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C & \\ & \pm D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A^T \\ B^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

for A, B, C, D of compatible dimensions. The inner dimension r is sometimes referred to as the rank of the factorization, even though $\text{rank} LDL^T \leq r$. If the overall result is expected to have a low rank, e.g.

$$LDL^T + LDL^T + LDL^T = \begin{bmatrix} L & L & L \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} D & & \\ & D & \\ & & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} L^T \\ L^T \\ L^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.6)$$

that inner dimension must not grow arbitrarily. Algorithm 3.1 shows how to compress a LRSIF based on the most significant eigenvalues, without imposing a maximum-rank condition, cf. Lang [15, Section 6.3.3]. The resulting factorization has a diagonal D and (potentially) a lower inner dimension.

Remark. It is worth to emphasize that LDL^T may even represent a full rank matrix X , albeit very inefficiently. In this case L and D are both square, i.e. $r = n$, such that they take twice as much memory as X . \triangle

Remark. Despite its name, L does not need to be (lower) triangular. Similarly, D does not need to be diagonal. In fact, the main results of Lang, Mena, and Saak [16] are only due to non-diagonal D , and are repeated in Chapter 4. \triangle

Rosenbrock Method

This chapter first gives an overview of Rosenbrock methods in the classical ODE setting, and states the selection of methods used in this thesis. Afterwards, these methods are reformulated for the matrix-valued DRE with low-rank solutions following Lang [15] and Mena [20].

4.1 Overview

Consider the autonomous initial value problem (IVP)

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = f(x) \\ x(t_0) = x_0 \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

on an equidistant time discretization $t_{n+1} = t_n + \tau$ for $n \geq 0$ and some $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$. Then, the s -stage Rosenbrock method Ros(s) reads

$$\begin{cases} x_{n+1} := x_n + \tau \sum_{j=1}^s b_j k_j \\ k_i := f\left(x_n + \tau \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \alpha_{ij} k_j\right) + \tau \mathcal{J} \sum_{j=1}^i \gamma_{ij} k_j \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, s, \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

where $\mathcal{J} := f'(x_n)$ denotes the Jacobian and $\alpha_{ij}, \gamma_{ij}, b_j$ are the determining coefficients of the method. Above formula follows the common notation of neglecting a subscript n for the stages $k_i = k_i(t_n)$. In the remainder, the analysis is restricted to methods with $\gamma_{11} = \dots = \gamma_{ss} =: \gamma$. For certain choices of γ , such a method is of order s or $s + 1$ [12].

This thesis focuses on a first-order one-stage method as well as a second-order two-stage method. The first method, Ros(1)

$$\begin{cases} x_{n+1} = x_n + \tau k_1 \\ (I - \gamma\tau \mathcal{J})k_1 = f(x_n) \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

having $b_1 = 1$, is A-stable for $\gamma \geq \frac{1}{2}$ [12, Table 6.3]. For a value of $\gamma = 1$, this method is often referred to as the *(linearly) implicit Euler* scheme, as it can be derived from the implicit Euler scheme by a degree-1 Taylor approximation of $f(x_{n+1})$ around $f(x_n)$.

The second method, Ros(2)

$$\begin{cases} x_{n+1} = x_n + \frac{3}{2}\tau k_1 + \frac{1}{2}\tau k_2 \\ (I - \gamma\tau \mathcal{J})k_1 = f(x_n) \\ (I - \gamma\tau \mathcal{J})k_2 = f(x_n + \tau k_1) - 2k_1 \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

having $\alpha_{21} = 1$, $b_1 = b_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, and $\gamma_{21} = -2\gamma$, was first described by Verwer et al. [31].⁸ This method is L-stable for $\gamma = 1 \pm \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$, cf. [12, Table 6.4], of which the larger option is chosen here.

4.2 Application to Differential Riccati Equations

In the context of the autonomous DRE

$$\dot{X} = \mathcal{R}(X) := C^T C + A^T X + X A - X B B^T X \quad (4.5)$$

the Jacobian $\mathcal{J} := \mathcal{R}'(X_n)$ is given by the Fréchet derivative. Since X is symmetric, \mathcal{J} is itself a Lyapunov operator,

$$\mathcal{R}'(X_n) : U \mapsto (A - B B^T X_n)^T U + U (A - B B^T X_n), \quad (4.6)$$

which causes the stage equations (4.2) to become ALEs. Let $\hat{A}_n := \gamma\tau(A - B B^T X_n) - \frac{1}{2}I$. Therefore, the implicit Euler scheme Ros(1) reads

$$\begin{cases} X_{n+1} = X_n + \tau K_1 \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_1 + K_1 \hat{A}_n = -\mathcal{R}(X_n), \end{cases} \quad (4.7)$$

while Ros(2) is given by

$$\begin{cases} X_{n+1} = X_n + \frac{3}{2}\tau K_1 + \frac{1}{2}\tau K_2 \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_1 + K_1 \hat{A}_n = -\mathcal{R}(X_n) \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_2 + K_2 \hat{A}_n = -\mathcal{R}(X_n + \tau K_1) + 2K_1. \end{cases} \quad (4.8)$$

The following sections describe efficient low-rank formulations of the methods above.

Remark. When formulating these methods for a generalized DRE, i.e. replacing

$$X \leftarrow E^T X E, \quad A \leftarrow E^{-1} A, \quad B \leftarrow E^{-1} B$$

and avoiding the inversion of E , the stages are generalized ALEs having the same right-hand sides as above, and coefficients E and $\hat{A}_n = \gamma\tau(A - B B^T X_n E) - \frac{1}{2}E$. \triangle

⁸The formulation (4.4) as in [31, Equation (3.4)] is based on $k_1 := \hat{k}_1$ and $k_2 := \hat{k}_2 - 2\hat{k}_1$, where \hat{k}_1 and \hat{k}_2 are the stages of the original form (4.2). Hence, b_1 and b_2 do not coincide with the coefficients of the first equation of (4.4).

4.2.1 Linearly Implicit Euler Scheme

The following construction goes back to Mena [20, Section 4.3.3] and Lang [15, Section 6.2.2]. Substituting $K_1 = \frac{1}{\tau}(X_{n+1} - X_n)$ into the stage equation, Ros(1) simplifies to a single Lyapunov equation for the next iterate X_{n+1} ,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{A}_n^T X_{n+1} + X_{n+1} \tilde{A}_n \\ = -\mathcal{R}(X_n) + \tilde{A}_n^T X_n + X_n \tilde{A}_n \end{aligned} \quad (4.9a)$$

$$= -C^T C - X_n B B^T X_n - \frac{1}{\tau} X_n, \quad (4.9b)$$

where $\tilde{A}_n := \frac{1}{\tau} \hat{A}_n = A - B B^T X_n - \frac{1}{2\tau} I$ and $\gamma = 1$. If $X_n = L D L^T$ is a LRSIF of rank $r \in \mathbb{N}$, the right-hand side may be written as

$$= -[C^T \quad L \quad L] \begin{bmatrix} I & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & D L^T B B^T L D & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \frac{1}{\tau} D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C \\ L^T \\ L^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.9c)$$

$$= -[C^T \quad L] \begin{bmatrix} I & \cdot \\ \cdot & D L^T B B^T L D + \frac{1}{\tau} D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C \\ L^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.9d)$$

$$=: -G S G^T \quad (4.9e)$$

using the update formula from Section 3.3, and compressing the redundant information. The result is a LRSIF of rank $q + r$. See Algorithm 4.1 for a summary.

Remark. For a generalized DRE it is $G = [C^T \quad E^T L]$ and S remains unchanged. \triangle

Remark. The generalized ALE on step 6 of Algorithm 4.1 will be solved using the ADI method, which will be presented in Chapter 5. In that context, note the low-rank update in step 3, which will be critical for an efficient implementation, cf. Section 3.2. For more details, refer to Section 7.1. \triangle

4.2.2 Second-Order Scheme

Instead of rewriting Ros(2) to be a single equation, this subsection describes how to use the first stage equation for a more efficient low-rank formulation of the second stage equation.

Algorithm 4.1: Low-Rank Linearly Implicit Euler Method

Input: Matrices E, A, B, C defining a generalized DRE (2.29), $X(t_0) = L_0 D_0 L_0^T$,

$\tau : t_n = t_0 + n\tau$ for $n \leq N$

Output: L_n, D_n such that $X(t_n) \approx X_n = L_n D_n L_n^T$, and $K_n = B^T X_n E$

```

1 for  $n \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$  do
2    $K_n \leftarrow (B^T L_n D_n)(L_n^T E)$ 
3    $\tilde{A}_n \leftarrow (A - \frac{1}{2\tau} E) - B K_n$ 
4    $G_n \leftarrow [C^T \quad E^T L_n]$ 
5    $S_n \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} I \\ (B^T L_n D_n)^T (B^T L_n D_n) + \frac{1}{\tau} D_n \end{bmatrix}$ 
6   Solve  $\tilde{A}_n^T X_{n+1} E + E^T X_{n+1} \tilde{A}_n = -G_n S_n G_n^T$ 
   for  $L_{n+1}, D_{n+1}$  such that  $X_{n+1} = L_{n+1} D_{n+1} L_{n+1}^T$ 
7 end
8  $K_N \leftarrow (B^T L_N D_N)(L_N^T E)$ 
    
```

Low-Rank Formulation of the Riccati Operator The following construction goes back to Lang et al. [16]. Suppose $X_n = LDL^T$ is a LRSIF of rank $r \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,

$$\mathcal{R}(LDL^T) = C^T C + A^T (LDL^T) + (LDL^T) A - (LDL^T) B B^T (LDL^T) \quad (4.10a)$$

$$= [C^T \quad A^T L \quad L \quad L] \begin{bmatrix} I & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & D & \cdot \\ \cdot & D & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & -DL^T B B^T LD \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C \\ L^T A \\ L^T \\ L^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.10b)$$

$$= [C^T \quad A^T L \quad L] \begin{bmatrix} I & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & D \\ \cdot & D & -DL^T B B^T LD \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C \\ L^T A \\ L^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.10c)$$

$$=: G^{(1)} S^{(1)} G^{(1)T} \quad (4.10d)$$

which is itself a LRSIF of rank $q + 2r$.

Remark. These off-diagonal D are another advantage of the LRSIF over the LRCF, which would have required complex arithmetic. \triangle

Remark. For a generalized DRE it is $G^{(1)} = [C^T \quad A^T L \quad E^T L]$ and $S^{(1)}$ remains unchanged. \triangle

Riccati Operator of a Shifted Argument The following construction is based on the work of Mena [20].⁹ Evaluating the Riccati operator is rather expensive. In the context of Ros(2) (4.8), the evaluation of \mathcal{R} necessary to compute the first stage K_1 is therefore reused for the computation of K_2 . First, expand the Riccati operator of a shifted argument

$$\mathcal{R}(X_n + \tau K_1) = \mathcal{R}(X_n) + \tau A^T K_1 + \tau K_1 A \quad (4.11a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \tau K_1 B B^T X_n - \tau X_n B B^T K_1 - \tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 \\ & = \mathcal{R}(X_n) - \tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 \\ & \quad + \tau(A - B B^T X_n)^T K_1 + \tau K_1(A - B B^T X_n) \end{aligned} \quad (4.11b)$$

and use that to rewrite the right-hand side of the second stage

$$\begin{aligned} & - \mathcal{R}(X_n + \tau K_1) + 2K_1 \\ & = - \mathcal{R}(X_n) + \tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 + 2K_1 \end{aligned} \quad (4.12a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \quad - \tau(A - B B^T X_n)^T K_1 - \tau K_1(A - B B^T X_n) \\ & = - \mathcal{R}(X_n) + \tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 \end{aligned} \quad (4.12b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \quad - \underbrace{(\tau(A - B B^T X_n) - I)^T}_{\frac{1}{\gamma} \hat{A}_n - (1 - \frac{1}{2\gamma})I} K_1 - K_1 \underbrace{(\tau(A - B B^T X_n) - I)}_{\text{ditto}} \\ & = - \mathcal{R}(X_n) + \tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 - \frac{1}{\gamma} \underbrace{(\hat{A}_n^T K_1 + K_1 \hat{A}_n)}_{-\mathcal{R}(X_n)} + (2 - \frac{1}{\gamma}) K_1 \end{aligned} \quad (4.12c)$$

$$= -(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma}) \mathcal{R}(X_n) + \tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 + (2 - \frac{1}{\gamma}) K_1 \quad (4.12d)$$

using the first stage equation. This allows a decomposition of K_2 according to

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} X_{n+1} = X_n + \frac{3}{2} \tau K_1 + \frac{1}{2} \tau K_2 \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_1 + K_1 \hat{A}_n = - \mathcal{R}(X_n) \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_{21} + K_{21} \hat{A}_n = \tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 + (2 - \frac{1}{\gamma}) K_1 \\ K_2 = (1 - \frac{1}{\gamma}) K_1 + K_{21}. \end{array} \right. \quad (4.13)$$

In anticipation of the next chapter, replace K_{21} by its negative. Then substituting K_2 into the update equation yields

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} X_{n+1} = X_n + (2 - \frac{1}{2\gamma}) \tau K_1 - \frac{1}{2} \tau K_{21} \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_1 + K_1 \hat{A}_n = - \mathcal{R}(X_n) \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_{21} + K_{21} \hat{A}_n = -(\tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 + (2 - \frac{1}{\gamma}) K_1). \end{array} \right. \quad (4.14)$$

⁹The original unfortunately contains many small mistakes, which have hopefully all been eliminated in preparation of Lang's dissertation [15] and, independently, for this thesis.

Finally, the right-hand side of the new second stage equation is formulated in LRSIF following Lang, Mena, and Saak [16]. Suppose $K_1 = T_1 M_1 T_1^T$, which allows to directly factor the right-hand side of the second stage equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & \tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 + \left(2 - \frac{1}{\gamma}\right) K_1 \\ &= T_1 \left[\tau^2 M_1 T_1^T B B^T T_1 M_1 + \left(2 - \frac{1}{\gamma}\right) M_1 \right] T_1^T \end{aligned} \quad (4.15a)$$

$$=: G^{(21)} S^{(21)} G^{(21)T} \quad (4.15b)$$

See Algorithm 4.2 for a summary.

Remark. For a generalized DRE it is $G^{(21)} = E^T T_1$ and $S^{(21)}$ remains unchanged. \triangle

Remark. Again, note the low-rank update in step 3 of Algorithm 4.2. \triangle

Algorithm 4.2: Low-Rank Second-Order Rosenbrock Method**Input:** Matrices E, A, B, C defining a generalized DRE (2.29), $X(t_0) = L_0 D_0 L_0^T$, $\tau : t_n = t_0 + n\tau$ for $n \leq N$ **Output:** L_n, D_n such that $X(t_n) \approx X_n = L_n D_n L_n^T$, and $K_n = B^T X_n E$

```

1 for  $n \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$  do
2    $K_n \leftarrow (B^T L_n D_n)(L_n^T E)$ 
3    $\hat{A}_n \leftarrow (\gamma\tau A - \frac{1}{2}E) - \gamma\tau B K_n$ 
   First Stage:
4    $G_n^{(1)} \leftarrow [C^T \quad A^T L_n \quad E^T L_n]$ 
5    $S_n^{(1)} \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} I & & \\ & \cdot & \\ & & D \end{bmatrix}$ 
6   Solve  $\hat{A}_n^T K_1 E + E^T K_1 \hat{A}_n = -G_n^{(1)} S_n^{(1)} G_n^{(1)T}$ 
   for  $T_1, M_1$  such that  $K_1 = T_1 M_1 T_1^T$ 
   Second Stage:
7    $G_n^{(21)} \leftarrow E^T T_1$ 
8    $S_n^{(21)} \leftarrow \tau^2 (B^T T_1 M_1)^T (B^T T_1 M_1) + (2 - \frac{1}{\gamma}) M_1$ 
9   Solve  $\hat{A}_n^T K_{21} E + E^T K_{21} \hat{A}_n = -G_n^{(21)} S_n^{(21)} G_n^{(21)T}$ 
   for  $T_{21}, M_{21}$  such that  $K_{21} = T_{21} M_{21} T_{21}^T$ 
   Next Iterate:
10   $L_{n+1} \leftarrow [L_n \quad T_1 \quad T_{21}]$ 
11   $D_{n+1} \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} D_n & & \\ & (2 - \frac{1}{2\gamma})\tau M_1 & \\ & & -\frac{1}{2}\tau M_{21} \end{bmatrix}$ 
12 end
13  $K_N \leftarrow (B^T L_N D_N)(L_N^T E)$ 

```


Alternating-Directions Implicit Method

The alternating-directions implicit (ADI) method goes back to Peaceman and Rachford [23]. It has originally been designed to solve linear systems $Ax = b$ for symmetric positive-definite $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and applied to elliptic and parabolic PDEs using a finite-difference scheme. This chapter first derives the method as a splitting method. Section 5.3 then applies the ADI to an ALE in LRSIF following Lang [15]. Finally, Section 5.4 describes how to choose the ADI parameters following Kürschner [14].

5.1 Parametrized Splitting Schemes

Many iterative methods solving $Ax = b$ can be written in a one-step *splitting* form

$$Mx^{k+1} = Nx^k + b \quad (5.1)$$

where $M - N = A$ and systems $Mx = d$ are “easy” to solve [11, Section 11.2.3]. These methods are *consistent* by construction, i.e. every solution to $Ax = b$ is a fixpoint of the iteration. Conversely, every fixpoint $x^{k+1} = x^k$ is a solution as well. Throughout the chapter, assume that M^{-1} exists. The method converges if the spectral radius $\rho(G) < 1$ for $G := M^{-1}N$ [11, Theorem 11.2.1]. G is called *iteration matrix* of the scheme.

The structure above is called *first normal form* of the method. Consistency is equivalent to $M - N = A$. The *second normal form* of a consistent linear iteration method reads

$$x^{k+1} = M^{-1}((M - A)x^k + b) = x^k - M^{-1}(Ax^k - b) \quad (5.2)$$

and $B := M^{-1}$ is called *matrix of the second normal form*.

A splitting method is called *parametrized* if the iteration matrix depends on the iteration, i.e. $A = M_k - N_k$ for $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The normal forms are thus given by

$$M_k x^{k+1} = N_k x^k + b, \quad (5.3a)$$

$$x^{k+1} = x^k - M_k^{-1}(Ax^k - b). \quad (5.3b)$$

An operator split and a method is further called *commuting* if M_k, N_k commute, i.e.

$$M_k N_k = N_k M_k \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N},$$

and *fully commuting* if M_*, N_* commute, i.e.

$$M_i N_j = N_j M_i \quad M_i M_j = M_j M_i \quad N_i N_j = N_j N_i \quad \forall i, j \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In the latter case, the order in which the steps defined by (M_0, N_0) to (M_k, N_k) are applied does not matter:

Proposition 5.1 (Permutation Invariance). Let $A = M_k - N_k$ be a fully permuting operator split. Then, the value of x^{k+1} given by the parametrized splitting method (5.3) does not depend on the order of the steps. \triangle

Proof. The following is a generalization of the proof of Li and White [17, Theorem 4.1]. Let $G_k := M_k^{-1}N_k$ denote the iteration matrix and $B_k := M_k^{-1}$ denote the matrix of the second normal form (5.3b). Observe that the matrices G_i, G_j as well as A, B_i, B_j commute for $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$, since $ab = ba \implies a^{-1}b = ba^{-1}$ for any a, b in a multiplicative group. Therefore, any neighboring steps may be exchanged,

$$\begin{aligned} x^{k+1} &= G_k x^k + B_k b \\ &= G_k (G_{k-1} x^{k-1} + B_{k-1} b) + B_k b \\ &= \underbrace{(G_k G_{k-1})}_{G_{k-1} G_k} x^{k-1} + \underbrace{(G_k B_{k-1} + B_k)}_{G_{k-1} B_k + B_{k-1}} b \end{aligned}$$

since $N_k = M_k - A$ implies $G_k = I_n - B_k A$ as well as

$$\begin{aligned} G_k B_{k-1} + B_k &= (I_n - B_k A) B_{k-1} + B_k \\ &= B_{k-1} - \underbrace{B_k A B_{k-1}}_{B_{k-1} A B_k} + B_k \\ &= B_{k-1} + (I_n - B_{k-1} A) B_k \\ &= B_{k-1} + G_{k-1} B_k. \end{aligned}$$

As any permutation may be obtained by exchanging neighboring configurations, thus x^k does not depend on the order of the steps. \square

A well known fact is that the iteration matrix G_k determines the behavior of the *error* $e^k := x^k - x^*$, where $Ax^* = b$. Due to the consistency of the method, $M_k x^* = N_k x^* + b$. Subtract this from the first normal form (5.3a) to obtain $M_k e^{k+1} = N_k e^k$ or, equivalently,

$$e^{k+1} = G_k e^k. \quad (5.4)$$

An interesting observation is that for commuting operator splits, the same recursion holds for the residual. This leads to an alternative formulation of the second normal form.

Proposition 5.2 (Recursive Residuals). Let $A = M_k - N_k$ define a commuting parametrized splitting method (5.3). Then, the *residual* $r^k := Ax^k - b$ adheres to

$$r^{k+1} = G_k r^k$$

where $G_k := M_k^{-1}N_k$ denotes the iteration matrix. \triangle

Proof. Due to $A = M_k - N_k$ it is $AM_k^{-1} = I - N_kM_k^{-1}$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 r^{k+1} &= Ax^{k+1} - b \\
 &= A(M_k^{-1}(N_kx^k + b)) - b \\
 &= M_k^{-1}N_k \underbrace{Ax^k}_{r^k + b} + \underbrace{AM_k^{-1}b - b}_{I - N_kM_k^{-1}} \\
 &= M_k^{-1}N_k r^k + \underbrace{(M_k^{-1}N_k - N_kM_k^{-1})b}_0.
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 5.3 (Recursive Increment Form). Let $A = M_k - N_k$ define a commuting parametrized splitting method (5.3). Then, the *increment* $v^k := -M_k^{-1}r^k$ defining the second normal form (5.3b),

$$x^{k+1} = x^k + v^k$$

adheres to

$$M_{k+1}v^{k+1} = N_kv^k$$

where $r^k := Ax^k - b$ denotes the residual. △

Proof. By Proposition 5.2 and $M_kN_k = N_kM_k$ it is

$$M_{k+1}v^{k+1} = -r^{k+1} = -M_k^{-1}N_k r^k = N_k(-M_k^{-1}r^k) = N_kv^k.$$

□

Remark. The above is a generalization of the ADI reordering for Lyapunov equations presented by Li and White [17, Section 4]. Their argument, which relies on Proposition 5.1, is outlined in Appendix A. Note that Corollary 5.3 does not require a fully commuting splitting method, nor does it restrict the initial value x^0 . △

Reasoning about the convergence of parametrized splitting schemes is not as straightforward as in the classical case. To the best knowledge of the author, only sufficient criteria and heuristics based on the following trivial theorem are known:

Theorem 5.4 (Convergence of Splitting Schemes). Let $A = M_k - N_k$ define a parametrized splitting method (5.3). The method converges to $x = A^{-1}b$ for all starting points x^0 if and only if $G_k \cdots G_0 \rightarrow 0$ where $G_k := M_k^{-1}N_k$. △

Proof. Follows directly from Equation (5.4). □

5.2 ADI as a Parametrized Splitting Scheme

Suppose $A = H + V$ for $A, H, V \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, and $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a solution to $Ax = b$. Then it is easy to see that

$$\begin{aligned} (H + \alpha I_n)x &= b - (V - \alpha I_n)x \\ (V + \beta I_n)x &= b - (H - \beta I_n)x \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$. Define the short-hand notation

$$\begin{aligned} H_k^+ &:= H + \alpha_k I_n & V_k^+ &:= V + \beta_k I_n \\ H_k^- &:= H - \beta_k I_n & V_k^- &:= V - \alpha_k I_n \end{aligned} \quad (5.6)$$

and convert the above into an iteration scheme

$$\begin{cases} H_k^+ x^{k+\frac{1}{2}} = b - V_k^- x^k \\ V_k^+ x^{k+1} = b - H_k^- x^{k+\frac{1}{2}}, \end{cases} \quad (5.7)$$

where the parameters $\alpha_k, \beta_k \in \mathbb{C}$ are free to choose for every iteration $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Obviously, every sub-step is a splitting scheme. In fact, the ADI as a whole can be seen as a parametrized splitting scheme. Substituting the intermediate step $x^{k+\frac{1}{2}}$ into the full step x^{k+1} leads to

$$V_k^+ x^{k+1} = b - \underbrace{H_k^- (H_k^+)^{-1}}_{(H_k^+)^{-1} H_k^-} (b - V_k^- \hat{x}^k). \quad (5.8)$$

Multiplying by H_k^+ then gives

$$H_k^+ V_k^+ x^{k+1} = H_k^- V_k^- x^k + \underbrace{(H_k^+ - H_k^-)}_{(\alpha_k + \beta_k) I_n} b. \quad (5.9)$$

Finally, multiplying by $(\alpha_k + \beta_k)^{-1}$ reveals the splitting formulation in its first normal form

$$\underbrace{(\alpha_k + \beta_k)^{-1} H_k^+ V_k^+}_{M_k} x^{k+1} = \underbrace{(\alpha_k + \beta_k)^{-1} H_k^- V_k^-}_{N_k} x^k + b. \quad (5.10)$$

Indeed, the splitting is consistent, $M_k - N_k = A$, since

$$\begin{aligned} H_k^+ V_k^+ &= HV + \alpha_k \beta_k I_n + \beta_k H + \alpha_k V \\ H_k^- V_k^- &= HV + \beta_k \alpha_k I_n - \alpha_k H - \beta_k V. \end{aligned} \quad (5.11)$$

Corollary 5.5 (Fully Commuting Splitting Scheme). The ADI is a fully commuting parametrized splitting scheme if H, V commute. \triangle

Proof. $H, V, \gamma I_n$ commute for any $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}$, and thus H_*^\pm, V_*^\pm commute. \square

Lemma 5.6 (Cayley Transformation). Let $A, E \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ with $-\alpha \notin \Lambda(A, E)$. The *generalized Cayley transformation* of a matrix pair (A, E) is defined by the rational matrix function

$$\mathcal{C}(A, E, \alpha, \beta) := (A + \alpha E)^{-1}(A - \beta E) = I_n - (\alpha + \beta)(A + \alpha E)^{-1}E.$$

Its eigenvalues are given by $(\lambda + \alpha)^{-1}(\lambda - \beta)$ for $\lambda \in \Lambda(A, E)$. If $\Lambda(A, E) \subseteq \mathbb{C}_-$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}_-$, then the spectral radius $\rho(\mathcal{C}(A, E, \alpha, \bar{\alpha})) < 1$. \triangle

Proof. Compare [14, Proposition 2.16]. \square

Assuming that H, V commute, the iteration matrix G_k for the ADI is therefore given as a sequence of Cayley transformations,

$$G_k := M_k^{-1}N_k = \underbrace{\left((H_k^+)^{-1} H_k^- \right)}_{\mathcal{C}(H, I, \alpha_k, \beta_k)} \underbrace{\left((V_k^+)^{-1} V_k^- \right)}_{\mathcal{C}(V, I, \beta_k, \alpha_k)}. \quad (5.12)$$

As will be motivated in the next section, $\beta_k = \bar{\alpha}_k$. In that case, if $\Lambda(H), \Lambda(V) \subseteq \mathbb{C}_-$ and $\alpha_k \in \mathbb{C}_-$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, then $\rho(G_k) < 1$ for all k . This is a reasonable starting point towards $G_k \cdots G_0 \rightarrow 0$, cf. Theorem 5.4, but not a necessary condition. However, if H, V commute, there exist parameters $\{(\alpha_k, \beta_k) \mid k \in \mathbb{N}\}$ such that the ADI shows superlinear convergence, see [3].

5.3 Application to Algebraic Lyapunov Equations

Consider the ALE

$$\mathcal{L}(X) := AX + XA^H = -W \quad (5.13)$$

where $W = W^T$.¹⁰ The Lyapunov operator $\mathcal{L} \equiv \mathcal{L}_L + \mathcal{L}_R$ naturally decomposes into left-multiplication $\mathcal{L}_L: X \mapsto AX$ and right-multiplication $\mathcal{L}_R: X \mapsto XA^H$. Furthermore, \mathcal{L}_L and \mathcal{L}_R commute:

$$\mathcal{L}_L \circ \mathcal{L}_R \equiv \mathcal{L}_R \circ \mathcal{L}_L \equiv X \mapsto AXA^H \quad (5.14)$$

All the operators above are linear and act on $\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. Apply the ADI in its intermediate-step formulation (5.7):

$$\begin{cases} (A + \alpha_k I_n)X_{k+\frac{1}{2}} = -W - X_k(A^H - \alpha_k I_n) \\ X_{k+1}(A^H + \beta_k I_n) = -W - (A - \beta_k I_n)X_{k+\frac{1}{2}} \end{cases} \quad (5.15)$$

The one-step formulation in its first normal form (5.10) reads:

$$(A + \alpha_k I_n)X_{k+1}(A + \bar{\beta}_k I_n)^H = (A - \beta_k I_n)X_k(A - \bar{\alpha}_k I_n)^H - (\alpha_k + \beta_k)W \quad (5.16)$$

¹⁰ Note that the position of the transpose differs from the usage in Chapter 4, e.g. Equations (4.7) and (4.8). Both variants are common and, hopefully, will not cause confusion. The notation in Chapter 4 is closer to performant implementations using matrices in column-major storage, while the notation in this chapter makes the low-rank formulation a little less verbose.

Choosing $\beta_k := \overline{\alpha_k}$ the above becomes Hermitian:

$$(A + \alpha_k I_n) X_{k+1} (A + \alpha_k I_n)^H = (A - \overline{\alpha_k} I_n) X_k (A - \overline{\alpha_k} I_n)^H - 2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) W \quad (5.17)$$

Remark. Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{R}$ and $A_+ := A + \alpha I_n \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$. As a mapping of matrices, $\mathcal{L}_R + \alpha I_{n^2} : \mathbb{C}^{n \times n} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ maps U onto $U A_+^H + \alpha U = U(A + \overline{\alpha} I_n)^H \neq U A_+^H$. Therefore, the notation is slightly more involved than in the previous section. Refer to Appendix B for more details on how to represent the application of a linear operator as the left-multiplication by a matrix. \triangle

Remark. Lang [15] formulates the ALE (5.13) in terms of the right-multiplication $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_R : X \mapsto X A^T$, $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_R \neq \mathcal{L}_R$. The ADI [15, Equation (2.23)] uses a somewhat inconsistent second step. This leads to the impression that the ADI is a single-parameter ADI having $\tilde{\beta}_k := \tilde{\alpha}_k$ instead of being a true two-parameter ADI where potentially $\alpha_k \neq \beta_k := \overline{\alpha_k}$. The one-step formulation [15, Equation (2.24)] is equivalent to Equation (5.17). \triangle

5.3.1 Low-Rank Formulation

Define the short-hand notation

$$\begin{aligned} A_k^+ &:= A + \alpha_k I_n \\ A_k^- &:= A - \overline{\alpha_k} I_n \end{aligned} \quad (5.18)$$

and let the low-rank factorizations

$$\begin{aligned} X_k &= L_k D_k L_k^H \\ W &= G S G^H \end{aligned} \quad (5.19)$$

for $G \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_G}$, $S \in \mathbb{R}^{n_G \times n_G}$ be given. Typically, $n_G \ll n$. Then, Equation (5.17) reads

$$(A_k^+ L_{k+1}) D_{k+1} (A_k^+ L_{k+1})^H = (A_k^- L_k) D_k (A_k^- L_k)^H - 2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) G S G^H \quad (5.20)$$

such that the ADI can be stated in LRSIF directly. Using the update formulas of Section 3.3, the iterates are build by successively adding column blocks of size n_G :

$$\begin{aligned} A_k^+ L_{k+1} &= [A_k^- L_k \quad G] \\ D_{k+1} &= \begin{bmatrix} D_k & \\ & -2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) S \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (5.21)$$

Using an initial value $X_0 = 0$, the k -th iterate has dimensions $L_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times k n_G}$ and $D_k \in \mathbb{R}^{k n_G \times k n_G}$. As a consequence, computing L_{k+1} requires $k n_G + n_G$ system solves and becomes increasingly expensive. This can be remedied by a reformulation according to Corollary 5.3.

In the notation of the previous section,

$$\begin{aligned} M_k : U &\mapsto (2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k))^{-1} (A_k^+) U (A_k^+)^H \\ N_k : U &\mapsto (2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k))^{-1} (A_k^-) U (A_k^-)^H \end{aligned} \quad (5.22)$$

such that Corollary 5.3 yields the following equivalent formulation of Equation (5.17):

$$\begin{cases} X_{k+1} = X_k + \tilde{V}_k, & A_k^+ \tilde{V}_k (A_k^+)^H = \frac{2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k)}{2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_{k-1})} (A_{k-1}^-) \tilde{V}_{k-1} (A_{k-1}^-)^H, \\ X_0 = 0, & A_0^+ \tilde{V}_0 (A_0^+)^H = -2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_0) W. \end{cases} \quad (5.23)$$

Assume a factorization of the increment $\tilde{V}_k = V_k Y_k V_k^H$ for $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, for $W = GSG^H$, the low-rank version of the initial value \tilde{V}_0 reads

$$\begin{aligned} A_0^+ V_0 &= G, \\ Y_0 &= -2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_0) S. \end{aligned} \quad (5.24)$$

Thus, the iteration of the increment $\tilde{V}_k = V_k Y_k V_k^H$ reads

$$\begin{aligned} A_k^+ V_k &= A_{k-1}^- V_{k-1} \\ Y_k &= \frac{2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k)}{2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_{k-1})} Y_{k-1} = -2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) S \end{aligned} \quad (5.25)$$

such that the overall iteration $X_{k+1} = X_k + \tilde{V}_k$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} L_{k+1} &= [L_k \quad V_k] \\ D_{k+1} &= \begin{bmatrix} D_k & \\ & Y_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_k & \\ & -2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) S \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (5.26)$$

Summing up, this leads to the low-rank procedure

$$\begin{cases} L_k = [V_0 \quad \cdots \quad V_{k-1}] \\ D_k = \begin{bmatrix} -2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_0) S & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & -2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_{k-1}) S \end{bmatrix} \\ A_k^+ V_k = A_{k-1}^- V_{k-1} \\ A_0^+ V_0 = G, \end{cases} \quad (5.27)$$

where $V_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_G}$ has constant dimensions. Therefore, only n_G system solves are necessary at any iteration k of the ADI. This method first appeared in the work of Benner, Li, and Truhar [4, Section 5].

This raises a couple of questions, that the following subsections aim to answer:

- (i) How to deal with the growing storage demand of the low-rank factors L_k and D_k ?

One may perform a column compression after any iteration using the technique described in Section 3.3.

- (ii) When should the iteration stop?

A traditional criterion is to stop when the residual reaches a certain threshold. This requires an efficient description of the residual.

- (iii) What happens if $\alpha_k \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{R}$?

Complex arithmetic is more expensive than real arithmetic. As will be discovered later, complex parameters occur in conjugated pairs. This allows a reformulation of the combined step, that only requires real arithmetic.

5.3.2 Low-Rank Stopping Criterion

Theorem 5.7 (Low-Rank Lyapunov Residual). The residual of the ADI, with $\beta_k := \overline{\alpha_k}$ and $X_0 = 0$ applied to the ALE (5.13), has a well-defined low-rank factorization compatible to $W = GSG^H$, $G \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n_G}$, $S \in \mathbb{C}^{n_G \times n_G}$, namely

$$\mathcal{L}(X_k) + GSG^H = R_k S R_k^H$$

for $R_k \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n_G}$ and $R_0 = G$. Furthermore, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} R_{k+1} &= R_k - 2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) V_k \\ V_k &= (A_k^+)^{-1} R_k \end{aligned}$$

where $V_k \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n_G}$ denotes the low-rank increment of Formula (5.27). \triangle

Proof. In the notation of the previous section, let r^k and ν^k denote residual and increment, respectively. Obviously, $r^0 := \mathcal{L}(0) + W = W = GSG^H$, hence $R_0 = G$. Due to Proposition 5.2,

$$r^{k+1} = G_k r^k = ((A_k^+)^{-1} A_k^-) R_k S R_k^H ((A_k^+)^{-1} A_k^-)^H$$

using the short-hand notation (5.18), and the iteration mapping $G_k \equiv M_k^{-1} \circ N_k$ as defined by Equation (5.22). This implies

$$R_{k+1} = ((A_k^+)^{-1} A_k^-) R_k = R_k - 2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) (A_k^+)^{-1} R_k, \quad (*)$$

using Lemma 5.6, i.e. R_k is well-defined $\forall k$.

By definition of the increment, $\nu^k := -M_k^{-1}(r^k)$, cf. Corollary 5.3, it holds

$$V_k Y_k V_k^H = (A_k^+)^{-1} R_k \underbrace{(-2 \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) S)}_{Y_k} R_k^H (A_k^+)^{-H},$$

i.e. $V_k = (A_k^+)^{-1} R_k$. Applying this to (*) yields the remaining equality. \square

Remark. The curious reader may compare the proof above to [14, Theorem 3.5]. \triangle

Still, the full residual $R_k S R_k^H \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ should never be assembled. Note that $R_k S R_k^H$ and $R_k^H R_k S \in \mathbb{C}^{n_G \times n_G}$ have the same spectra, cf. [16, Remark on p. 56]. Therefore, both are diagonalizable such that

$$\|R_k S R_k^H\|_2 = \rho(R_k S R_k^H) = \rho(R_k^H R_k S) = \|R_k^H R_k S\|_2. \quad (5.28)$$

Suppose the residual is real, i.e. $R_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_G}$. Using the well-known inequality

$$\|X\|_2 \leq \|X\|_F \leq \sqrt{r} \|X\|_2 \quad (5.29)$$

for any matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ where $r := \text{rank } X$, one may replace the spectral norm in Equation (5.28) and [15, Algorithm 2.2] by the Frobenius norm. This leads to the stopping criterion

$$\|R_k^H R_k S\|_F \leq \varepsilon \|G^H G S\|_F \quad (5.30)$$

for a user-specified threshold $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$. Since $r \leq n_G$, this relation implies

$$\|R_k^H R_k S\|_2 \leq \varepsilon \sqrt{n_G} \|G^H G S\|_2, \quad (5.31)$$

which is slightly weaker than the behavior of Lang's implementation [15]. Replacing ε by $n_G^{-1/2} \varepsilon$ leads to a slightly more restrictive stopping criterion compared to [15].

5.3.3 Low-Rank Double-Step

Proposition 5.8 (Complex Conjugated Parameters). Suppose $A, W \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $X_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is real for a fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$, i.e. $G, R_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_G}$ and $S \in \mathbb{R}^{n_G \times n_G}$ as defined in Theorem 5.7. If the next parameters form a complex conjugated pair, $\alpha_{k+1} = \overline{\alpha_k}$, then the iterate after that, X_{k+2} is real again. More specifically,

$$\begin{aligned} R_{k+2} &= R_k - 4 \text{Re}(\alpha_k) (\text{Re}(V_k) + \delta_k \text{Im}(V_k)) \\ V_{k+1} &= \overline{V_k} + 2\delta_k \text{Im}(V_k) \end{aligned}$$

for $\delta_k := \text{Re}(\alpha_k) / \text{Im}(\alpha_k)$. \triangle

Proof. Compare Kürschner [14, Theorem 4.2]. \square

Corollary 5.9 (Low-Rank Double-Step). Suppose that L_k, D_k are real-valued for a fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$. If the next parameters form a complex conjugated pair, $\alpha_{k+1} = \overline{\alpha_k}$, an equivalent low-rank update is given by

$$L_{k+2} = [L_k \quad \hat{V}_k \quad \hat{V}_{k+1}]$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{V}_k &= \sqrt{2} (\text{Re}(V_k) + \delta_k \text{Im}(V_k)) \\ \hat{V}_{k+1} &= \sqrt{2} (\delta_k^2 + 1) \text{Im}(V_k) \end{aligned}$$

and D_{k+2} remains as in Equation (5.27). \triangle

Proof. The double-step reads

$$X_{k+2} = X_k + V_k Y_k V_k^H + V_{k+1} Y_{k+1} V_{k+1}^H$$

where $Y_k = -2\operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k)S = Y_{k+1}$, since $\operatorname{Re}(\alpha_k) = \operatorname{Re}(\alpha_{k+1})$. By Proposition 5.8, the combined increment is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & V_k Y_k V_k^H + V_{k+1} Y_{k+1} V_{k+1}^H \\ &= V_k Y_k V_k^H + (\overline{V_k} + 2\delta_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)) Y_k (\overline{V_k} + 2\delta_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k))^H \\ &= V_k Y_k V_k^H + (\overline{V_k}) Y_k (\overline{V_k})^H \\ &\quad + 2\delta_k (\overline{V_k}) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H \\ &\quad + 2\delta_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k (\overline{V_k})^H \\ &\quad + 4\delta_k^2 \operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H \\ &= 2\operatorname{Re}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Re}(V_k)^H + 2\operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H \\ &\quad + 2\delta_k \operatorname{Re}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H - 2i\delta_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H \\ &\quad + 2\delta_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Re}(V_k)^H + 2i\delta_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H \\ &\quad + 2\delta_k^2 \operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H + 2\delta_k^2 \operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H, \end{aligned}$$

which by grouping the terms in each column yields

$$\begin{aligned} &= 2(\operatorname{Re}(V_k) + \delta_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)) Y_k (\operatorname{Re}(V_k) + \delta_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k))^H \\ &\quad + 2(\delta_k^2 + 1) \operatorname{Im}(V_k) Y_k \operatorname{Im}(V_k)^H \\ &= \hat{V}_k Y_k \hat{V}_k^H + \hat{V}_{k+1} Y_{k+1} \hat{V}_{k+1}^H. \end{aligned}$$

This last formula requires only real arithmetic, in nice analogy to the real-valued residual of Proposition 5.8. \square

5.4 Parameter Selection

After deriving a suitable structure of the ADI for the ALE, the shift parameters $\{\alpha_k : k \in \mathbb{N}\}$ are still to be determined. Classical choices of *pre-computed* values include optimal Wachspress shifts [32, 33] and heuristic Penzl shifts [24]. These try to globally minimize $\rho(G_K \cdots G_0)$ for a fixed number of ADI steps $K \in \mathbb{N}$, and estimates for the spectra $\Lambda(H)$ and $\Lambda(V)$. This thesis employs the first ansatz of *self-generating shifts* described by Kürschner [14, Section 5.3], so-called $V(u)$ -shifts, which aim at minimizing $\rho(G_k|_{\operatorname{span} V_k})$ separately for each iteration k , which does not require any information on the spectra of H or V .

As mentioned at the end of Section 5.2, a local criterion like this does in general not guarantee convergence. However, these parameters seemed to outperform the aforementioned pre-computed approaches in the experiments of [14].

The general idea is to restrict A onto $\mathcal{Q} := \text{span } N \subseteq \mathbb{C}^n$ for some matrix N and take its (stable) eigenvalues. These so-called *Ritz values* are defined as

$$\Lambda(Q^H A Q, Q^H E Q) \cap \mathbb{C}_-, \quad (5.32)$$

where $Q \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times d}$ is an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{Q} , $d := \dim \mathcal{Q}$. In the context of $V(u)$ -shifts for LRSIF ADI [16], choose

$$N := [V_{j-1} \ \cdots \ V_{j-u}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times un_G}. \quad (5.33)$$

The overall procedure is summarized in Algorithm 5.1.¹¹

Remark. Due to the low-rank structure, only that part of the iteration mapping (5.12) is considered, which operates on one of the low-rank factors. This part is exactly $\hat{G}_k := \mathcal{C}(A, E, \alpha_k, \bar{\alpha}_k)$. Suppose $\lambda \in \Lambda(A, E) \cap \mathbb{R}$, $\lambda < 0$. Notice how choosing $\alpha = \beta := \lambda$ in Lemma 5.6 maps λ onto 0 as an eigenvalue of $\mathcal{C}(A, E, \lambda, \lambda)$. Above Ritz values act similarly on $\hat{G}_k|_{\text{span } N}$. \triangle

To obtain an orthonormal basis, recall that \mathbb{R}^n and \mathbb{R}^{un_G} decompose into

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{R}^{un_G} &= \ker N \oplus \text{span } N^T \\ \mathbb{R}^n &= \ker N^T \oplus \text{span } N \end{aligned} \quad (5.34)$$

and that $NN^\dagger = N(N^T N)^\dagger N^T$ is the projection onto $\text{span } N$, where $(\cdot)^\dagger$ denotes the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse [28]. This leads to an implicit orthogonalization procedure. Note that $N^T N$ is symmetric positive semi-definite. Hence, it permits a real eigendecomposition

$$N^T N = \hat{N} \hat{D} \hat{N}^T, \quad \hat{N}^T \hat{N} = I_r, \quad \hat{D} = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_r), \quad \lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_r > 0,$$

where $r = \text{rank } N = \text{rank } N^T N \leq un_G$. The Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse is then given by $(N^T N)^\dagger := \hat{N} \hat{D}^{-1} \hat{N}^T$. Finally,

$$Q := N \hat{N} \hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r} \quad (5.35)$$

is an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{Q} . First, Q is orthonormal:

$$Q^T Q = \hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \hat{N}^T (N^T N) \hat{N} \hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} (\hat{N}^T \hat{N}) \hat{D} (\hat{N}^T \hat{N}) \hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \hat{D} \hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} = I_r$$

Second, $\text{span } N = \text{span } Q$. By (5.34), for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^{un_G}$ it is

$$\begin{aligned} Nx &= NN^T y + 0 && \text{for some } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \\ &= N(N^T N \hat{x} + 0) && \text{for some } \hat{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{un_G} \\ &= N(\hat{N} \hat{D} \hat{N}^T) \hat{x} \\ &= N \hat{N} \hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \hat{y} && \text{for } \hat{y} := \hat{D}^{\frac{3}{2}} \hat{N}^T \hat{x} \in \mathbb{R}^r, \end{aligned}$$

i.e. $\text{span } N \subseteq \text{span } Q$. This implies equality, since $\text{span } Q \subseteq \text{span } N$ (trivial).

¹¹Algorithm 5.1 positions the transposes as the previous chapter does, cf. footnote 10 on page 25.

The derivation above neglected zero eigenvalues of $N^T N$, whose eigenvectors are syzygies of $\text{span } N$. Indeed, let $(\varepsilon, s) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^{un_G}$ be an eigenpair of $N^T N$ with $\|s\|_2 = 1$. Then,

$$\|Ns\|_2^2 = s^T (N^T N s) = \varepsilon \|s\|_2^2 = \varepsilon, \quad (5.36)$$

which for $\varepsilon = 0$ reveals linearly dependent columns of N . In that sense, small eigenvalues λ_* correspond to nearly linearly dependent columns. It is therefore advised to only consider the first $d \leq r$ eigenvalues

$$\lambda_* \geq \varepsilon \lambda_1 \quad (5.37)$$

for some $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$, e.g. a multiple of the machine precision, $\varepsilon := nu_{\text{mach}}$. This corresponds to replacing \hat{N} by its first d columns, \hat{D} by its leading diagonal block of size d , and $\text{span } N$ by $\text{span}(\hat{N} \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_d, 0, \dots) \hat{N}^T)$, while the overall formula (5.35) remains unchanged. Thus, the procedure leads to $d \leq r \leq un_G$ new shifts.

Algorithm 5.1: Low-Rank Alternating-Directions Implicit Method

Input: Matrices E, A, G, S defining a generalized ALE (2.31) where $W = GSG^T$,
tolerance $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$

Output: L, D such that $X \approx LDL^T$

Compute initial parameters, cf. Section 5.4:

```

1  $Q \leftarrow \text{orth } G$ 
2  $\{\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots\} \leftarrow \Lambda(Q^H A Q, Q^H E Q) \cap \mathbb{C}_-$ 
   Perform actual ADI:
3  $R_0 \leftarrow G$ 
4  $k \leftarrow 0$ 
5 repeat
6   if  $\alpha_k$  is not available then
7      $Q \leftarrow$  if  $\alpha_{k-1} \in \mathbb{R}$  then  $\text{orth } V_{k-1}$  else  $\text{orth } [\hat{V}_{k-2} \ \hat{V}_{k-1}]$ 
8      $\{\alpha_k, \alpha_{k+1}, \dots\} \leftarrow \Lambda(Q^H A Q, Q^H E Q) \cap \mathbb{C}_-$ 
9   end
10   $Y_k \leftarrow -2 \text{Re}(\alpha_k) S$ 
11   $A_k^+ \leftarrow A^T + \alpha_k E$ 
12  if  $\alpha_k \in \mathbb{R}$  then
13    Perform single step, cf. Subsections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2:
14    Solve  $A_k^+ V_k = R_k$  for  $V_k$ 
15     $L_{k+1} \leftarrow [L_k \ V_k], \ D_{k+1} \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} D_k & \\ & Y_k \end{bmatrix}$ 
16     $R_{k+1} \leftarrow R_k - 2\alpha_k E V_k$ 
17     $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
18  else
19    Perform double-step, cf. Subsection 5.3.3:
20    Solve  $A_k^+ V_k = R_k$  for  $V_k$ 
21     $\delta_k \leftarrow \text{Re}(\alpha_k) / \text{Im}(\alpha_k)$ 
22     $\hat{V}_k \leftarrow \sqrt{2}(\text{Re}(V_k) + \delta_k \text{Im}(V_k))$ 
23     $\hat{V}_{k+1} \leftarrow \sqrt{2}(\delta_k^2 + 1) \text{Im}(V_k)$ 
24     $L_{k+2} \leftarrow [L_k \ \hat{V}_k \ \hat{V}_{k+1}], \ D_{k+2} \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} D_k & & \\ & Y_k & \\ & & Y_k \end{bmatrix}$ 
25     $R_{k+2} \leftarrow R_k - 4 \text{Re}(\alpha_k) E (\text{Re}(V) + \delta_k \text{Im}(V))$ 
26     $k \leftarrow k + 2$ 
27  end
28  Compress  $L_k, D_k$  if necessary, cf. Algorithm 3.1
29 until  $\|R_k^T R_k S\|_F \leq \varepsilon \|G^T G S\|_F$ , cf. Subsection 5.3.2

```


Parareal Method

The parareal method is a parallel-in-time integration scheme to solve ODEs. It goes back to Lions, Maday, and Turinici [18], though the most common form also used in this thesis first appeared in Baffico et al. [2]. This chapter first describes the general properties of the parareal method, and derives it as a Newton method following Gander and Vandewalle [10]. Lastly, Section 6.3 adapts the method for LRSIFs.

6.1 Overview

Consider the autonomous IVP

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u} = f(u) \\ u(t_0) = u_0 \end{cases} \quad (6.1)$$

over the time span $[t_0, t_f]$. In practical applications, one is typically interested in a high temporal resolution trajectory of u . Let $F(t, t_0, u_0) \approx u(t)$ be such a fine/high-precision solver for the IVP above. However, applying F to the whole time span may be too slow. The goal therefore is to apply F on several time slices $[t_{n-1}, t_n]$ in parallel, $1 \leq n \leq N$, with the help of a faster but lower-precision solver $G(t, t_0, u_0) \approx u(t)$. Therefore, fix a coarse discretization $t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_N = t_f$. Then the parareal method to compute $U_n \approx u(t_n)$ reads

$$\begin{cases} U_{n+1}^0 := G(U_n^0) \\ U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k) \end{cases} \quad (6.2)$$

where $U_0^* := u_0$ and $G(U_n) := G(t_{n+1}, t_n, U_n)$, $F(U_n) := F(t_{n+1}, t_n, U_n)$ integrate from t_n to t_{n+1} . The general data dependencies between the parareal iterates U_n^k are shown in Figure 6.1. Observe that in any topological order of that graph, the coarse solutions $G(U_n^k)$ for any fixed k need to be computed sequentially over n .

Notice how in general each coarse solution $G(\cdot)$ is needed twice. Therefore, a reasonable scheduling pattern of the directed acyclic graph of Figure 6.1 that exploits good data locality is a pipeline of stages n which compute

$$\dots, G(U_{n-1}^k), U_n^k, F(U_{n-1}^k), \dots, \quad (6.3)$$

where the arrows denote data dependencies or transmissions from and to the adjacent stages. Dependencies within a stage are not shown. Note how this pattern correspond to

Figure 6.1: Dependencies between parareal values U_n^k

the rows of Figure 6.1. Each stage n holds $G(U_{n-1}^{k-1})$ and $F(U_{n-1}^{k-1})$ in memory, receives U_{n-1}^k from its predecessor, and sends U_n^k to its successor. However, there is no need that all stages n compute the same number of refinements k , due to the following proposition.

Proposition 6.1 (Diagonal Convergence). Stage n of the parareal method converges after at most $k = n$ iterations:

$$U_n^k = U_n^n = F(U_{n-1}^{n-1}) \quad \forall k \geq n$$

△

Proof. Due to $U_0^k = u_0$ for all k , it follows by induction $\forall k \geq n$:

$$\begin{aligned} U_{n+1}^{k+1} &:= F(U_n^k) + G(U_n^{k+1}) - G(U_n^k) \\ &= F(U_n^n) + G(U_n^n) - G(U_n^n) = F(U_n^n) \end{aligned}$$

□

The early iterates U_n^k for $k = n$ thus have fewer dependencies between them, cf. Figure 6.2. Furthermore, the same reasoning as in the proof of Proposition 6.1 can be applied if stage n converges after refinement $k < n$, i.e. $U_n^{k+1} \approx U_n^k$. In that case, stage $n+1$ converges the refinement thereafter,

$$\begin{aligned} U_{n+1}^{k+1} &:= F(U_n^k) + G(U_n^{k+1}) - G(U_n^k) \\ &\approx F(U_n^k) + G(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k) = F(U_n^k). \end{aligned} \tag{6.4}$$

Therefore, assuming G is well conditioned, there is no need to compute $G(U_n^{k+1})$.

Figure 6.2: Dependencies between parareal values U_0^0, \dots, U_2^2

Following Proposition 6.1, the parareal method converges after $k = N$ iterations at the latest, at which point the parareal solutions equal the fine solution, $U_n^N = F(U_{n-1}^N)$ for $1 \leq n \leq N$. In practice, however, it may converge much earlier than that, i.e. $k \ll N$. Limiting the number of refinements to $k \leq K$, and assuming that F , G , and communication all take constant time, the expected timeline of a parareal execution is shown in Figure 6.3. Note how the diagram corresponds to Figure 6.1; the slope of the $k = 0$ face depends on the runtime of G .

Figure 6.3: Schematic parareal timeline. Time passed and refinement k both increase to the right, the parareal stage n increases to the top. The $k = K$ boundary will not be visible if $K \geq N$.

Figure 6.4: First couple of refinements k of the parareal method applied to the linear problem (6.5). The stages n are decoded by color, with dots denoting U_n^k and lines denoting $F(\cdot, t_{n-1}, U_{n-1}^k)$. The dashed gray curve represents the exact solution.

Example 6.2 (Linear ODE). Let $\phi := \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ denote the golden ratio and let $\kappa := \frac{2}{\pi} \log \phi$. Consider the IVP

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \kappa & -1 \\ 1 & \kappa \end{bmatrix} u \\ u(0) = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ -\kappa \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \quad (6.5)$$

for $t \in [0, 2\pi]$. Let $N := 5$, $\tau := 2\pi/N$, and $t_n := n\tau$ for $n \in \{0, \dots, N\}$. Further, let F and G be implicit Euler schemes using step sizes $\tau/100$ and τ , respectively. If the fine solver internally uses a finer mesh, by Proposition 6.1, the global solution x may be retrieved at that fine resolution $\tau/100$.

Figure 6.4 shows the first couple of iterations of the parareal method applied the problem above. For a fixed refinement k , the values $U_n^k \approx u(t_n)$ (represented by dots) are computed in sequence, cf. the horizontal traces in Figure 6.1. After that, the fine

solutions $F(U_n^k)$ (represented by lines) can then be computed in parallel. The parareal method only ensures convergence of U_n^k . Therefore, before convergence is reached, the high-resolution trajectories are discontinues at t_n . Furthermore, note that the overall accuracy of the parareal solution is limited by the accuracy of F , which explains the remaining gap between the colored and the gray line. \triangle

6.2 Parareal as a Multiple Shooting Method

The following construction is based on Gander and Vandewalle [10]. Consider again the autonomous IVP

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u} = f(u) \\ u(t_0) = u_0 \end{cases} \quad (6.1)$$

Note that the solution $u : [t_0, t_f] \rightarrow V$ depends on the initial value U_0 . For a discretization $t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_N = t_f$ define the local problems

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u}_n = f(u_n) \\ u_n(t_n) = U_n \end{cases} \quad (6.6)$$

for $n \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$ and determine suitable initial values U_n . Watch the slight abuse of notation in u_0 for the initial value $u_0 \in V$ and the solution $u_0 : [t_0, t_1] \rightarrow V$ to the first local problem. The local solutions $u_n : [t_n, t_{n+1}] \rightarrow V$ represent a global solution to the IVP (6.1) if

$$\mathcal{F}(U_0, \dots, U_{N-1}) := \begin{pmatrix} U_0 - u_0 \\ U_1 - u_0(t_1, U_0) \\ \vdots \\ U_{N-1} - u_{N-2}(t_{N-1}, U_{N-2}) \end{pmatrix} \stackrel{!}{=} 0. \quad (6.7)$$

Let $U := (U_0, \dots, U_{N-1})$ and $\mathcal{J}(U)$ denote the Jacobian of \mathcal{F} at U . Then, Newton's method reads

$$U^{k+1} = U^k - \mathcal{J}(U^k)^{-1} \mathcal{F}(U^k) \quad (6.8)$$

or, equivalently, avoiding the inversion of the Jacobian,

$$\begin{bmatrix} I & & & & \\ -\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial U_0}(t_1, U_0) & I & & & \\ & & \ddots & & \\ & & & \ddots & \\ & & & -\frac{\partial u_{N-2}}{\partial U_{N-2}}(t_{N-1}, U_{N-2}) & I \end{bmatrix} (U^{k+1} - U^k) = -\mathcal{F}(U^k). \quad (6.9)$$

Writing the above in separate equations yields

$$\begin{cases} U_0^{k+1} = u_0 \\ U_n^{k+1} = u_n(t_{n+1}, U_n^k) + \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial U_n^k}(t_{n+1}, U_n^k)(U_n^{k+1} - U_n^k). \end{cases} \quad (6.10)$$

Lastly, choosing a fine propagator $F(U_n^k) := F(t_{n+1}; t_n, U_n^k) \approx u_n(t_{n+1}, U_n^k)$, a coarse propagator G according to

$$G(U_n^{k+1}) - G(U_n^k) \approx \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial U_n^k}(t_{n+1}, U_n^k)(U_n^{k+1} - U_n^k) \quad (6.11)$$

as well as initial values $U_{n+1}^0 = G(U_n^0)$, reveals the parareal method of Baffico et al. [2],

$$\begin{cases} U_0^* = u_0 \\ U_{n+1}^0 = G(U_n^0) \\ U_{n+1}^{k+1} = F(U_n^k) + G(U_n^{k+1}) - G(U_n^k). \end{cases} \quad (6.2 \text{ revisited})$$

A Taylor expansion of $G(U_n^{k+1}) \approx u_n(t_{n+1}, U_n^{k+1})$ around $G(U_n^k)$ justifies Equation (6.11).

6.3 Application to Low-rank Symmetric Indefinite Factorizations

Let the LRSIFs

$$\begin{aligned} G(U_n^{k+1}) &= L_{G,k+1} D_{G,k+1} L_{G,k+1}^T \\ F(U_n^k) &= L_{F,k} D_{F,k} L_{F,k}^T \\ G(U_n^k) &= L_{G,k} D_{G,k} L_{G,k}^T \end{aligned} \quad (6.12)$$

be given. Using the low-rank update formulas described in Section 3.3, the parareal update (6.2) reads

$$\hat{L} \hat{D} \hat{L}^T := \begin{bmatrix} L_{G,k+1} & L_{F,k} & L_{G,k} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} D_{G,k+1} & & \\ & D_{F,k} & \\ & & -D_{G,k} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} L_{G,k+1}^T \\ L_{F,k}^T \\ L_{G,k}^T \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6.13)$$

Note the dowdate in the last block component. The actual low-rank representation of U_{n+1}^{k+1} is set to a column compression of $\hat{L} \hat{D} \hat{L}^T$ using Algorithm 3.1.

Implementation and Experimental Results

Julia is a multi-paradigm language created by Bezanson et al. at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) [6]. While development on the language began in 2009, its version 1.0 has been released in 2018. This chapter first covers the general properties of the two Julia packages created during the work on this thesis. Both of these packages have an automated test suite with a coverage of well over 90%. Lastly, the packages are applied to the Rail benchmark problem [22].

7.1 DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl

This package is concerned with sequential DRE solvers only. The general user interface has been inspired by `DifferentialEquations.jl` [26], and looks like this:

```
1 prob = GDREProblem(E, A, B, C, X0, tspan)
2 alg = Ros1()
3 sol = solve(prob, alg; dt=dt)
```

Besides `Ros1()` and `Ros2()`, which correspond to the algorithms described in Chapter 4, there also is a `Ros4()` solver. It is based on Lang [15, Appendix A] and only supports the dense case. The `GDREProblem` type is parametrized on the type of the initial value `X0`, by which the proper ALE solver is selected via runtime dispatch on `solve()`. Dense initial values are represented by the built-in `Matrix` type,¹² and lead to a direct ALE solver from `MatrixEquations.jl` [30]. Initial values in LRSIF are represented by the new `LDLT` type, and lead to the iterative ADI solver described in Chapter 5.

Representation of Low-Rank Matrices Suppose $X = LDL^T$ and $X = LDL^T(L, D)$ are mathematical and Julia representations of the same objects, $L \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$, $D \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$. Then, the internal representation of X consists of lists `[L]` and `[D]`, such that updates may be performed lazily by merely collecting all the summands, cf. Section 3.3. Compression of X is performed once these lists contain 10 elements or more, or if the equivalent inner dimension is too large, $r \geq \frac{1}{2}n$. This causes a compression every 10 iterations of the ADI or earlier. This is not configurable yet, cf. Code Snippet 7.2. Note that line 19 mainly guards the situation when a user accesses `L` and `D` (via iteration: `L, D = X`), compression is not performed twice. All internal usages guarantee the assumption in the comment above line 19.

¹²<https://docs.julialang.org/en/v1.6/stdlib/LinearAlgebra/>

Code Snippet 7.2: Definition of LDL^T and addition (+) of LRSIF objects. The compression, `compress!()`, is described in Algorithm 3.1.

```
1 struct LDLT{TL,TD}
2   Ls::Vector{TL}
3   Ds::Vector{TD}
4 end
5
6 function Base.:(+)(Xs::LDLT{TL,TD}...) where {TL,TD}
7   Ls = TL[]
8   Ds = TD[]
9   for X in Xs
10    append!(Ls, X.Ls)
11    append!(Ds, X.Ds)
12  end
13  X = LDLT{TL,TD}(Ls, Ds)
14  maybe_compress!(X)
15 end
16
17 function compression_due(X::LDLT)
18   # If there is only one component, it has likely already been compressed:
19   length(X.Ls) == 1 && return false
20   # Compression is due every couple of modifications:
21   length(X.Ls) >= 10 && return true
22   # Compression is due if rank is too large:
23   n = size(X, 1)
24   r = rank(X)
25   return r >= 0.5n
26 end
27
28 function maybe_compress!(X::LDLT)
29   compression_due(X) || return X
30   compress!(X)
31 end
```

Representation of Shifted Matrices Recall that the Rosenbrock methods yield ALEs, whose system matrices are sparse matrices shifted by a low-rank matrix, cf. \tilde{A}_n in step 3 of Algorithm 4.1 and \hat{A}_n in step 3 of Algorithm 4.2. Within the ADI, these matrices are updated by another sparse matrix, cf. A_k^+ in step 11 of Algorithm 5.1. Overall, taking Ros(1) as an example, the system to be solved with is

$$A_k^+ = \left((A_n - \frac{1}{2\tau}E)^T + \alpha_k E \right) - K_n^T B^T. \quad (7.1)$$

This structure, however, is completely hidden from the ADI code via

```
1  $\tilde{A}$  = LowRankUpdate(A - E/(2 $\tau$ ), -1, B, K)
2 R = LDLT(G, S)
3 lyap = GALEProblem(E,  $\tilde{A}$ , R)
4 solve(lyap, ADI())
```

Thereby, the ADI transposes \tilde{A} via `adjoint()`, and adds the sparse $\alpha_k E$ via (+) without losing the `LowRankUpdate` structure. Its main feature, however, is solving the corresponding linear system via the backslash operator (`\`) using the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula, cf. Section 3.2. See Code Snippet 7.4 for the basic definition of `LowRankUpdate` and the aforementioned functions.

7.2 ParaReal.jl

This section describes the general properties of the `ParaReal.jl` package. It has been designed with the following requirements in mind:

- (i) Schedule each stage on a separate process.

This is a sensible default for the application at hand, which is memory bound for typical problem sizes. Yet, the scheduling strategy should be modifiable/extendable.

- (ii) Allow the data transferred be variable in size.

This is necessary to transmit LRSIFs of varying rank and, therefore, storage size depending on n (and k).

- (iii) Do not transfer the final solution data back to the calling/managing process.

For fine resolutions, the storage requirements easily reach hundreds of gigabytes. The overall solution might not fit in memory of a single compute node. Therefore, it has to be possible that each stage n saves its local (fine) solution along $[t_{n-1}, t_n]$ directly to disk, without sending it to the calling process first.

On top of that:

- (iv) The parareal implementation has to be modular, i.e. easy to use/adapt for other problems than LRSIF formulations of DRE.

Code Snippet 7.4: Definition of `LowRankUpdate`, a lazy representation of the shifted linear system $A + \alpha^{-1}UV$, as well as addition (+) of a sparse matrix, and left-division (\) using the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula, cf. Section 3.2.

```
1 struct LowRankUpdate{TA,T,TU,TV}
2     A::TA
3      $\alpha$ ::T
4     U::TU
5     V::TV
6 end
7
8 function Base.adjoint(AUV::LowRankUpdate)
9     A,  $\alpha$ , U, V = AUV
10    LowRankUpdate(A',  $\alpha'$ , V', U')
11 end
12
13 function Base.:(+)(AUV::LowRankUpdate, E::AbstractMatrix)
14     @assert issparse(E)
15     A,  $\alpha$ , U, V = AUV
16     LowRankUpdate(A+E,  $\alpha$ , U, V)
17 end
18
19 function Base.:(\)(AUV::LowRankUpdate, B::AbstractVecOrMat)
20     A,  $\alpha$ , U, V = AUV
21
22     FA = factorize(A)
23     A-1B = FA \ B
24     A-1U = FA \ U
25
26     S =  $\alpha$  * I + V * A-1U
27     S-1VA-1B = S \ (V * A-1B)
28
29     X = A-1B - A-1U * S-1VA-1B
30     return X
31 end
```

Requirement (i) is achieved by the abstract type `Schedule`, whose sole subtype (for now) is `ProcessesSchedule`. It takes a list of N worker/process ids, each executing one stage. Future strategies may be implemented by defining new subtype of `Schedule`, e.g. `ThreadsSchedule` using threads on a single process, `HybridSchedule`, which uses both threads and processes, and `DaggerSchedule`, which uses the abstractions provided by `Dagger.jl`.¹³

Requirement (ii) is trivial to fulfill using Julia's `RemoteChannel` data type. Requirement (iv) imposes a non-specific naming scheme for user interface functions and the name of the unknown, as to not clash with the standard nomenclatures of other disciplines.¹⁴ The next section will describe the user interface of the `ParaReal.jl` package, and how to cope with requirement (iii).

7.2.1 User Interface

In applications one is usually interested in a high temporal resolution, while the parareal method is only used to obtain “fast” convergence. Therefore, the `ParaReal.jl` package distinguishes between a local solution along $[t_{n-1}, t_n]$ and its final value,

$$\begin{aligned} F(U_{n-1}^k) &= \text{value}(\text{fsolve}(\text{prob})) \\ G(U_{n-1}^k) &= \text{value}(\text{csolve}(\text{prob})), \end{aligned}$$

where `prob` is an instance of the global IVP (6.1) restricted to the local time slice $[t_{n-1}, t_n]$ and initial value U_{n-1}^k . The actual solver functions `csolve` (“coarse”) and `fsolve` (“fine”) are provided as arguments to `ParaReal.Algorithm()`. In order to support custom IVP types, a user has to define methods for `initial_value()` to obtain the global initial value U_0 , and `remake_prob()` to adjust the global problem for the local time slice and initial value. For more details, refer to the documentation of the respective functions available from within Julia.

In order to support new solution types, a custom implementation of the parareal update formula (6.2) may be needed. This can be specified as an optional third argument to `ParaReal.Algorithm`. The default is `ParaReal.default_update!()`, whose implementation is given in Code Snippet 7.5. Adding methods to `default_update!()` is not recommended. Any custom implementation of the parareal update formula must follow the interface of `default_update!()`.¹⁵

The remainder of this section describes a complete example of a user-defined problem type ($N = 3, K = 2$). The problem type will be a mere placeholder that forwards its initial value, while the solver functions will count the applications of F and G a particular solution is composed of.

¹³<https://github.com/JuliaParallel/Dagger.jl>

¹⁴For example, many parareal papers use U to name the unknown, many matrix ODE papers use X , and the widely-used `DifferentialEquations.jl` package [26] uses u .

¹⁵A function whose name ends with an exclamation mark signals that it (may) modify its arguments, i.e. that it may operate in-place. This, however, is only a guideline within the Julia community.

Code Snippet 7.5: Default implementations of the parareal update formula (6.2)

```

1 default_update!(_, Gk, Fk-1, Gk-1) = Gk + Fk-1 + (-Gk-1) # out-of-place
2 default_update!(Uk::Array, Gk, Fk-1, Gk-1) = @. Uk = Gk + Fk-1 - Gk-1 # in-place

```

Start by launching some worker processes and loading the necessary packages:

```

1 using ParaReal
2 using Distributed: addprocs, @everywhere
3
4 addprocs(3)
5 @everywhere using ParaReal

```

Next, define the problem type and ensure that its definition is available on all processes. The only requirement to the problem type is to have a `tspan` field.¹⁶ In the context of ODEs, this should not clash with any other notation.

```

6 @everywhere begin
7     struct SomeProblem
8         v
9         tspan
10    end
11    ParaReal.initial_value(p::SomeProblem) = p.v
12    ParaReal remake_prob(::SomeProblem, v, tspan) = SomeProblem(v, tspan)
13 end

```

The solution type will hold counters of the applications of F and G :

```

14 @everywhere begin
15     struct Counters
16         F::Int
17         G::Int
18     end
19     ParaReal.value(c::Counters) = c
20     # Needed by default parareal update implementation:
21     Base.:(+)(c1::Counters, c2::Counters) = Counters(c1.F + c2.F, c1.G + c2.G)
22     Base.:(-)(c::Counters) = c
23 end

```

Define the solver functions, problem instance, and execute the parareal pipeline. The solver functions are defined as closures, such that they can be serialized and transferred to the worker processes. Note that this code is only executed on the managing process:

```

24 inc_F = (p::SomeProblem) -> Counters(p.v.F + 1, p.v.G)
25 inc_G = (p::SomeProblem) -> Counters(p.v.F, p.v.G + 1)

```

¹⁶Alternatively, it must support `getproperty(prob, :tspan)`.

```

26 tspan = (0., 42.) # does not matter here
27 prob = SomeProblem(Counters(0, 0), tspan)
28 sol = solve(
29     ParaReal.Problem(prob),
30     ParaReal.Algorithm(inc_G, inc_F);
31     maxiters=2,
32     # disable convergence checks, which call norm(::Counters)
33     nconverged=typemax(Int),
34     # do not evaluate default rtol, which calls size(::Counters, 1)
35     rtol=0.0,
36 )

```

Lastly, extracting the final values U_1^1 , U_2^2 , and U_3^2 via

```

37 ParaReal.value(sol.stages[1])
38 ParaReal.value(sol.stages[2])
39 ParaReal.value(sol.stages[3])

```

yields:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \text{Counters}(1, 0), \text{ since} & U_1^1 = F(U_0) \\
 \text{Counters}(2, 0), \text{ since} & U_2^2 = F(F(U_0)) \\
 \text{Counters}(3+2+2, 2+4+4), \text{ since} & U_3^2 = G(F(F(U_0))) + F(U_2^1) - G(U_2^1) \\
 & U_2^1 = G(F(U_0)) + F(G(U_0)) - G(G(U_0))
 \end{array}$$

The full trajectory of the fine solver may be extracted using `ParaReal.solution()`. However, `solution` and `value` are identical in the example above, cf. line 19. Code Snippet 7.7 shows the recommended pattern of storing the fine solutions directly from the worker processes via `ParaReal.fetch_from_owner()`.

7.2.2 JIT Compilation and Warm-Up

Julia is a just-in-time (JIT) compiled language [6], which means that code is compiled just before it is first executed, unless it has already been compiled. Therefore, unless the code has been compiled ahead-of-time (AOT), only the second execution of code is fast. This effect is called *warm-up*. As mentioned in Chapter 6, computing the coarse solutions $G(U_n^*)$ is essentially a sequential operation over all n . The computations of $F(U_n^*)$ can only be parallelized after such a global coarse solve. Therefore, it is critical that the individual coarse solutions are available as fast as possible.

In order to describe the runtime of the present parareal implementation, let t_F and t_G denote the runtime of F and G , respectively. Let N be the number of stages $1 \leq n \leq N$, and K be the number of refinements $0 \leq k \leq K$. Let $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$ be the overhead imposed on the computation of each first coarse solution $G(U_n^0)$, and $t_{\text{warm-up}}$ be a general global overhead.

Code Snippet 7.7: Store fine parareal solutions directly from the worker processes. This works well as a blueprint for `DrWatson._wsave(dir, sol)` [8].

```

1 using DrWatson, ParaReal
2 using ParaReal: fetch_from_owner
3
4 # Assume solution to be given:
5 sol::ParaReal.Solution
6
7 # Ensure output directory exists:
8 mkpath(dir)
9
10 @sync for sref in sol.stages
11     @async fetch_from_owner(sref) do s::ParaReal.Stage
12         sol = ParaReal.solution(s)
13         tmin, tmax = extrema(sol.t)
14         fname = joinpath(dir, "t=$tmin:$tmax.h5")
15         # Write 'sol' to 'fname', e.g. via
16         DrWatson.wsave(fname, sol)
17     end
18 end

```

Further, the following assumptions are made:

- (i) t_F and t_G are constant, i.e. do not depend on n, k .
- (ii) The time to compute the actual value U_n^k is negligible, cf. Code Snippet 7.5.
- (iii) The overhead to check for convergence is negligible.
- (iv) Communication time is negligible.
- (v) All stages n compute K refinements, i.e. $k_n = K \forall n$.

The runtime may then be estimated using

$$\hat{t}_{\text{par}} := t_{\text{warm-up}} + \underbrace{N \cdot (t_{\text{ramp-up}} + t_G)}_{\substack{\text{stages } 1 \leq n \leq N \\ \text{refinement } k = 0}} + \underbrace{K \cdot (t_F + t_G)}_{\substack{n=N \\ 1 \leq k \leq K}} + t_F, \quad (7.2)$$

where the final t_F is to compute the best fine solution available. These assumptions are compatible to the generic timeline Figure 6.3. As will be described later,

$$t_{\text{warm-up}} + t_{\text{ramp-up}} = t_{\text{compile}(G)} + t_{\text{other}}, \quad (7.3)$$

i.e. the goal is to offset/reduce the ramp-up delay $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$ at the cost of a one-time overhead $t_{\text{warm-up}}$. $t_{\text{compile}(G)}$ denotes the compile time of G .

Figure 7.1: Timeline diagrams comparing the effect of JIT compiler warm-up. Left: $N = 8$ processes running on two compute nodes (4 threads/process), right: $N = 4$ processes running on a laptop. Top: no warm-up, middle: warming up coarse solver G (csolve), bottom: warming up coarse and fine solver F (fsolve).

warm-up	N	K	$t_{\text{warm-up}}$	$t_{\text{ramp-up}}$	t_G	t_F	t_{par}	\hat{t}_{par}	$\left \frac{\hat{t}_{\text{par}} - t_{\text{par}}}{t_{\text{par}}} \right $
none	8	7	0.00	10.45	1.40	13.69	215.85	214.04	0.008
G	8	7	11.00	1.78	1.38	14.05	155.98	158.32	0.015
G and F	8	7	24.66	1.81	1.39	14.00	171.88	171.89	<0.001
none	4	3	0.00	9.89	0.69	6.76	70.99	71.41	0.006
G	4	3	10.56	1.83	0.74	7.57	50.88	53.32	0.048
G and F	4	3	19.36	1.84	0.69	6.89	58.61	59.14	0.009

Table 7.1: Measurements corresponding to Figure 7.1 based on Equation (7.2). The actual runtime is denoted by t_{par} . t_F and t_G are estimated as the median, $t_{\text{warm-up}}$ as the maximum of their respective runtimes. $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$ is taken as the mean delay between adjacent $G(U_n^0)$ minus t_G . All timings are in seconds.

Sequential JIT compilation Without any precautions,

$$t_{\text{warm-up}} = 0,$$

JIT compilation of G happens sequentially, as computing $G(U_n^k)$ is essentially sequential over n . This effect is especially severe if the executors of different parareal iterations (n, k) do not share the results of code compilation. These executors may be processes, threads (pthreads), or tasks (green threads). For the present implementation, there is a one-to-one mapping between processes and stages n , which means the compilation happens exactly once per stage n and is reused between refinements k .¹⁷ This is visible in the first row of Figure 7.1 by the first occurrences of G for each stage n , which marks the computation of $G(U_n^0)$, whose execution time includes compilation time. Therefore, the first occurrences of G take substantially longer than the subsequent ones. The computation of the parareal update has a negligible duration, and is therefore not shown in the timeline plot, cf. assumption (ii).

Parallel AOT compilation Since `ParaReal.jl` is independent of F and G as well as the actual data type of the underlying IVP, full AOT compilation is difficult, and has to be done by users of the package. A more naive approach is to manually warm up critical parts of the code by executing them before they are actually needed. In the context of `ParaReal.jl`, doing so allows to perform the compilation in parallel, which significantly decreases the time to compute all coarse solutions $G(U_n^*)$. This is visible in the middle and bottom rows of Figure 7.1, where

$$\begin{aligned} t_{\text{warm-up}} &= t_{\text{compile}(G)} + t_G \quad \text{and} \\ t_{\text{warm-up}} &= t_{\text{compile}(G)} + t_G + t_{\text{compile}(F)} + t_F, \end{aligned}$$

respectively. Warming up both F and G has (as expected) a negligible effect on $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$, while adding a major overhead to \hat{t}_{par} as generally $t_F \gg t_G$.

Precompilation Besides reducing the delay of executing F and G , it is also important to reduce the delay of any code from `ParaReal.jl` that does not depend on them. The package is merely responsible for orchestrating the execution of the parareal iterations (n, k) . Therefore, the delay of the first execution of `ParaReal.jl` code is dominated by type inference.¹⁸ The time spent on type inference can be minimized by precompilation, which happens when the package is first loaded, and whose results are cached and reused when the package is loaded again. Exploiting this is highly non-trivial and out of the scope of this thesis.¹⁹

¹⁷As of the writing of this thesis, Julia does not reuse code compiled between processes.

¹⁸At least it likely is. Taking measurements is highly non-trivial and out of the scope of this thesis. For more details see: <https://julialang.org/blog/2020/08/invalidations/>

¹⁹https://julialang.org/blog/2021/01/precompile_tutorial/

Numerical Results Refer to Table 7.1 for the measurements corresponding to Figure 7.1. They are based on dense first-order Rosenbrock methods G and F applied to the Rail benchmark [22], taking 1 step ($\tau = 45 \text{ s}/N$) and 10 steps ($\tau = 45 \text{ s}/10N$), respectively. The relative errors in the final column show that the assumptions on page 48 are reasonable in this context. Note that $K = N - 1$, which is due to Proposition 6.1.

In the case of no warm-up, $t_{\text{warm-up}} = 0$, the overall compilation overhead caused by G scales linearly in N . If G is instead being warmed up, that overhead is constant and depends only on the underlying problem and solver. $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$ is significantly reduced in this case. There is no point in warming-up F as well. However, the remaining t_{other} includes compilation time for communications, e.g. to serialize the data types representing U_n^k , and to establish a connection between adjacent pipeline stages.²⁰ This still leaves a linear overhead in the number of stages N and potential for further improvements, as ideally $t_{\text{ramp-up}} = 0$. For the remainder of the thesis, G will always be warmed up.

7.2.3 Lack of Asynchronous Data Transfer

A common strategy to improve CPU utilization is to perform data transfers between processes asynchronously. Julia offers the `RemoteChannel` data structure for this purpose. As of the writing of this thesis, a `RemoteChannel` is not thread-safe.²¹ More specifically, it must be used from thread 1 of each process. This means that in order to asynchronously send the interface values U_n^{k+1} from stage n to the next, one would have to move the calls to F and G off of thread 1. The reason is that many implementations of F and G do not have an implicit (cooperative) yield point to Julia’s runtime, such that no task can run asynchronously on thread 1 next to the task executing F and G . This is particularly true for code that does not require IO, e.g. for many methods from Julia’s `LinearAlgebra` standard library, which internally call LAPACK.

The solution described in the previous paragraph is not yet implemented, i.e. all data transfers are synchronous. This causes gaps visible in Figure 7.1 after G and before F , where the processor is essentially idle. In general, a gap ends shortly before G starts on the next stage.²²

Another effect is that the iterations (n, k) for which $n + k \geq N$ show noticeably smaller gaps. The reason is twofold. The last stage N does not need to send any data, therefore has no JIT warm-up delay for the first iteration $k = 0$ and almost no gap in the diagram. This causes the next refinement $k = 1$ of the previous stage $N - 1$ to have a noticeably smaller gap as well, since its transmission code has already been compiled. This effect

²⁰By default, connections between processes are established when they are first used. Here, only the connections between the calling process and the worker processes, each executing a pipeline stage, have been created.

²¹<https://github.com/JuliaLang/julia/issues/37706>

²²There is one exception to this for $N = 4$ and no warm-up. The last yellow box on stage $n = 2$ in the top-right plot, $F(U_1^1)$, starts “too early” because $G(U_1^1)$ happens to finish before $G(U_2^0)$, and the Julia runtime has been able to schedule the receiving code one gap earlier.

propagates back-to-front through the still running pipeline stages.

The exact size of the gap between the computations of $G(U_{n-1}^k)$ and $F(U_{n-1}^k)$ of stage n is determined by how much the stages are out-of-sync. Assuming that

$$t_F > t_{\text{compile}(G)} + t_G \quad (7.4)$$

this includes for $n + k < N$

- (i) the overhead t_{other} , which includes e.g. the compilation time of any transmission code, and
- (ii) for $k \geq 1$ and no warm-up the overhead $t_{\text{compile}(G)}$ that, depending on the perspective, $G(U_n^{k-1})$ on the next stage finishes late, or $G(U_{n-1}^k)$ on the current stage finished early.²³

The last point causes the current stage to then “finish late” as well, from the perspective of the previous stage. For the first row of Figure 7.1, effect (ii) shadows (i), while for the remaining rows effect (ii) is essentially zero.

7.2.4 Early Convergence

Due to Theorem 2.2, later parareal stages are expected to require fewer Newton refinements than earlier stages to reach convergence. Each stage determines whether it has converged locally based on

$$\|U_n^k - U_n^{k-1}\| \leq \varepsilon \max\{\|U_n^k\|, \|U_n^{k-1}\|\} \quad (7.5)$$

for a user-specified threshold $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$ and number of successive k . In the case of the LRSIF $U_n^k = LDL^T$, the norm is evaluated as $\|L^T LD\|_F$, cf. Subsection 5.3.2, while the distance $\|\cdot - \cdot\|$ uses the low-rank downdate formula, cf. Section 3.3. For other custom data structures, a user has to define corresponding methods for the `ParaReal.dist()` and `LinearAlgebra.norm()` functions.

Therefore, if stage n has converged (locally), it may defer the computation of a refinement k until the previous stage $n - 1$ finished computing its refinement $k + 1$. That is, the number of refinements computed may differ by at most one from stage to stage, i.e. $k_{n+1} \geq k_n - 1$, where k_n denotes the last refinement computed by stage n . These effects are best to be seen in Figure 7.2, which corresponds to the reference solution of Figure 7.7 to be described in Subsection 7.3.2. This timeline also shows when the stages n are waiting for input, which may be a new initial value U_{n-1}^k or the signal that the previous stage finished. In that case, stage n may safely finish as well, since k_{n-1} will not increase any further. If none of the stages reached the maximum number of iterations, i.e. $k_n < K$ for all n , this situation is referred to as global convergence.

²³Note how assumption (7.4) is false for the hardware used in $N = 4$, which causes the outlier described in the previous footnote.

To summarize all effects described so far, the revised schematic timeline plot is shown in Figure 7.3, cf. Figure 6.3 for the expected schematic timeline. With respect to Figure 7.1, the faces $k = K$ and therefore early convergence are not visible. The face $n + K \geq N$ is most pronounced in the top left diagram. For large N , $N \gg K$, that effect will be negligible for the overall runtime of the parareal algorithm.

7.2.5 Parallel Scaling

Common metrics to compare parallel codes with are *speedup* $t_{\text{seq}}/t_{\text{par}}$ and *parallel efficiency* $t_{\text{seq}}/P \cdot t_{\text{par}}$, where t_{seq} denotes the runtime of the fastest sequential algorithm to solve a problem, t_{par} the runtime of a parallel algorithm solving the same problem, and $P \in \mathbb{N}$ denotes the number of processors the parallel code is executed on. These timings, and therefore the metrics as well, depend on the size of the problem. Usually, t_{seq} is not available and therefore estimated as the sequential runtime of the parallel algorithm.

In the context of the parareal method, the size of the problem refers to the number of steps of the fine solver or the resolution of the output trajectory. Instead of estimating t_{seq} as the sum of all F and G evaluated, a more relevant comparison is the theoretical runtime of the fine solver F over the whole time span. Therefore, let \hat{t}_{seq} be the total duration of the most recent fine solutions computed,

$$\hat{t}_{\text{seq}} := \sum_{n=1}^N t_F(n, k_n), \quad (7.6)$$

where k_n is the latest refinement k computed on stage n , and $t_F(n, k)$ denotes the runtime of $F(U_{n-1}^k)$. In Subsection 7.2.2, $t_F(n, k)$ had been assumed to be constant, cf. assumption (i) on page 48. However, as will be described in the next section, for the LRSIF methods this is not true.

As mentioned at the beginning of Section 7.2, there is a one-to-one mapping between stages n and processes. This means that the parallel efficiency has to be evaluated for $P = N$, which yields a very low parallel efficiency. Despite that, the speedups are quite good from a user's/engineer's perspective for larger N . Refer to Table 7.3 for the measurements corresponding to the numerical results to be discussed in the next section.

As early stages $n \leq K$ only compute $k = n$ refinements,²⁴ their processes become idle even before late stages receive their first U_n^0 , cf. e.g. left column of Figure 7.1. These processes may easily be reused, resulting in fewer processors being necessary, $P < N$, to obtain the same timeline. However, these processes must be warmed up only once, since the warm-up calls to G would not be executed in parallel. Refer to e.g. Nielsen et al. [21] for a more advanced scheduling strategy to better utilize given hardware.

²⁴Technically, they only compute $k = n - 1$ refinements and then directly take the fine solution $F(U_{n-1}^{n-1})$, which had already been evaluated for U_n^{n-1} , cf. Proposition 6.1.

Figure 7.2: Restarted parareal computations to maintain $k_{n+1} \geq k_n - 1$. Top: full timeline of dense parareal algorithm of order 4 coarse and fine solvers applied to the Rail benchmark [22], $N = 450$. This corresponds to the reference solution mentioned in Figure 7.7. Bottom: zoom to first stages $1 \leq n \leq 20$.

Figure 7.3: Revised schematic timeline diagram of `ParaReal.jl` implementation for N stages and K refinements. The warm-up block is to increase the slope of the $k = 0$ face, cf. Subsection 7.2.2. The dotted line is due to the lack of asynchronous data transfer for $n + k \geq N$, cf. Subsection 7.2.3. The dashed line indicates early convergence for $k_{n+1} < k_n$, cf. Subsection 7.2.4.

7.2.6 Parallel Programming Pitfalls

This subsection collects pitfalls in Julia in a parallel programming environment, that occurred during the development of this thesis.

Julia provides the `@sync` macro to wait for tasks launched in the enclosed block. Internally, it waits for the tasks to complete, collects any errors and re-throws them in a grouped exception, if any. However, it does so sequentially, by which the first task waited for may shadow the failure of the next task, such that the whole block enclosed by `@sync` reached a `deadlocked`.²⁵ There is an experimental eager version,²⁶ that waits concurrently, but it only reports the first failure without cancelling the remaining tasks. Also, it does not provide a handle on the tasks still running, such that the user has to do the bookkeeping. In general, as of the time of writing this thesis, there does not seem to be a recommended way to handle cancellation using the standard library, especially in a distributed environment.

By default, unhandled concurrent errors are transient, cf. Code Snippet 7.8.²⁷ That means that if a background task fails, not only keeps the program running, it does not

²⁵<https://github.com/JuliaLang/julia/issues/32677>

²⁶<https://github.com/JuliaLang/julia/pull/34198>

²⁷<https://github.com/JuliaLang/julia/issues/10405>

Code Snippet 7.8: Transient concurrent errors. The bash variable/`?` contains the return code of the last program.

```
1 $ julia --version
2 julia version 1.6.2
3
4 $ julia -e 'throw(Exception)'
5 ERROR: Exception
6 Stacktrace:
7  [1] top-level scope
8     @ none:1
9
10 $ echo $?
11 1
12
13 $ julia -e '@async throw(Exception); sleep(1)'
14
15 $ echo $?
16 0
```

even print an error.²⁸ It is not easy to let unhandled concurrent errors crash the whole program. More severely, in a distributed environment, a failed task on one machine may easily cause a different machine to reach a deadlock, cf. the previous paragraph. It is the user's (or the library developer's) responsibility to make errors observable,²⁹ and to make sure that the whole computation is properly cancelled.

It would be very handy, if users could configure Julia to crash on unhandled exceptions. Golang³⁰ for example does this by default.³¹ In a distributed environment, it would be nice if users could configure Julia to crash all processes (workers and manager), if a single crashed process is unhandled. Also, if a process fails, it should be easy to obtain the stack traces of all running tasks. Golang for example supports this via the environment variable `GOTRACEBACK=all`.³² `ParaReal.jl` tries to detect all exceptions and cancels the whole pipeline if a stage fails.

Sometimes, the Julia internal code fails to issue a command on a worker process.³³ It would be very handy if Julia would be able to discover when this happens and just try again. `ParaReal.jl` tries 3 times to start a stage, if it did not fail from a user error.

²⁸<https://github.com/JuliaLang/julia/pull/27722>

²⁹<https://github.com/JuliaLang/julia/pull/39518>

³⁰Golang may not be widely used in scientific computing, but it is much more widespread in general. As its parallel features are about as expressive as Julia's, it may serve as an example nonetheless.

³¹<https://go.dev/blog/defer-panic-and-recover>

³²https://pkg.go.dev/runtime#hdr-Environment_Variables

³³<https://discourse.julialang.org/t/77864>

7.3 Numerical Results

This section summarizes the results of applying the aforementioned methods to the Rail benchmark [22] of size $n = 371$ described in e.g. Example 2.1. Note that the algorithms are formulated for the problem stated in forwards time,

$$\begin{cases} E^T \dot{X}E = C^T C + A^T XE + E^T XA - E^T XBB^T XE \\ E^T X(t_0)E = \frac{1}{100} C^T C \end{cases} \quad (7.7)$$

but it's common practice to plot the results in the time corresponding to the underlying OCP, i.e. $E^T \tilde{X}(t_f)E = C^T C/100$.

As described in Chapter 2, one is mainly interested in the accuracy of the feedback matrix $K := B^T XE \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times n}$. For this purpose, the trajectory $K_{1,77}$ is characteristic due to its relatively large amplitude [16]. Furthermore, the (global) relative error

$$\frac{\|K(t) - K_{\text{ref}}(t)\|_F}{\|K_{\text{ref}}(t)\|_F} \quad (7.8)$$

is analyzed w.r.t. a reference solution computed with the dense 4th order method described by Lang [15, Appendix A]. Any error at $t = 45$ s is not shown, as it is zero due to the boundary condition of the DRE, which would distort the overall diagram.

The tolerances for both the ADI and parareal method, cf. Equation (5.30) in Subsection 5.3.2 and Equation (7.5) in Subsection 7.2.4, are chosen to be $\varepsilon := n u_{\text{mach}}$ where u_{mach} denotes machine precision and $n = 371$ refers to the problem dimension. The ADI may perform up to 100 iterations. A LRSIF is compressed every 10 iterations or earlier, if the inner dimension r reaches $\frac{1}{2}n$, cf. Section 7.1. Furthermore, each of the $N = 450$ parareal stages requires two successive refinements without significant change for (local) convergence, while computing at most $K = 10$ parareal refinements.

Remark. In this subsection, n may denote the problem dimension $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, or the time stop t_n , which is also related to the parareal stage n corresponding to the time span $[t_{n-1}, t_n]$, in which case $1 \leq n \leq N$. Furthermore, K may denote the feedback matrix $K = B^T XE$, or the maximum number of parareal refinements $k_n \leq K$ computed per stage n . The particular meaning should be clear from its context. \triangle

7.3.1 Sequential Solvers

Figure 7.4 shows the results of the Rosenbrock schemes described in Chapter 4, both in a dense and a LRSIF formulation. The low-rank variants are expected to perform identically to their dense counterparts, which for Ros(1) is true. However, there is a small difference between the second order methods for $t \leq 44$ s, which destroys the order of LRSIF 2 for about $t \leq 35$ s. The general downward trend of the errors as t approaches 0s is due to the L-stability of the methods and the constant limit, cf. Theorem 2.2.

Figure 7.4: Several Rosenbrock schemes applied to the problem of Example 2.1. Each scheme performs 450 steps ($\tau = 100$ ms). Top: trajectory of $K_{1,77}$ (same as Lang et al. [16, Fig. 1]), bottom: relative error (7.8) compared to reference solution (900 steps of dense Rosenbrock scheme of order 4). Left: global time span [0s, 45s], right: zoom to [43.2s, 45s] (highlighted on the left).

Figure 7.5: Relative error (7.9) in K between low-rank and dense solvers

The problem of LRSIF 2 can be confirmed with the (global) relative error

$$\frac{\|K_{\text{LRSIF}}(t) - K_{\text{Dense}}(t)\|_F}{\|K_{\text{Dense}}(t)\|_F} \quad (7.9)$$

between low-rank and dense variants of the same algorithm, cf. Figure 7.5. For Ros(1) this value is within margin, since $nu_{\text{mach}} \approx 10^{-13}$. However, for Ros(2) there is a significant error from the very first iteration at $t = 44.9$ s. This error stays about constant for the remainder of the time span.

As mentioned in Example 3.2, the rank of X should not get much larger than 113 along its trajectory. LRSIF 1 fulfills that expectation, as shown in Figure 7.6. It grows quickly for $t > 44$ s and seems to trend towards a plateau for $t < 30$ s. LRSIF 2, however, does not seem to stabilize, which results in significantly larger ranks for about $t < 40$ s.

Remark. Lang, Mena, and Saak [16, p. 63] noted a problem with the low-rank version of Ros(2) as well. The error behavior here looks similar to [16, Fig. 1], keeping in mind that here the step size is $100\times$ larger and that the results are compared to dense solvers instead of LRCF ones. \triangle

The rank of the solution $X(t_n)$ has a major effect on the runtime of the next Rosenbrock step. Recall that Ros(1) leads to an ALE whose right-hand is (a compression of) a LRSIF of rank $q + r$ where $r := \text{rank } X(t_n)$ denotes the rank of the previous Rosenbrock iterate, cf. Equation (4.9). Similarly, the right-hand side of the first stage of Ros(2) is (a compression) of rank $q + 2r$, cf. Equation (4.10). The rank of the ADI iterate thus grows by about that amount. In the worst case, this causes a compression to be performed after every iteration of the ADI.

Figure 7.6: Numerical rank of low-rank sequential solutions X to the Rail problem, cf. Lang [15, Figure 6.6b].

7.3.2 Parareal Solvers

Figure 7.7 shows the results of the parareal method described in Chapter 6 for dense and LRSIF algorithms and several order combinations. Again, the schemes should perform identically for dense and LRSIF storage. As expected due to the problem discovered for LRSIF 2, this is true only for the parareal schemes of order 1/1 for their coarse/fine solver. The reference solution has been computed with a dense order 4/4 parareal scheme. Its $K_{1,77}$ trajectory is not shown as it would be indistinguishable from the other solutions.

For the methods involving LRSIF 2, the relative error (7.8) in Figure 7.7 reveals the typical discontinuities at the interval bounds before convergence is reached, cf. Figure 6.4, for $n > K = 10$ or $t \leq 43.9$ s. But even for $t > 43.9$ s the error of the low-rank variants is noticeably larger. This effect has only been visible for $t < 35$ s in the purely sequential setting, cf. Figure 7.4. What looked like a more or less constant error in the previous subsection, seems to be diverging in Figure 7.7 for LRSIF 2/2 as t approaches $-\infty$, which is in stark contrast to the otherwise downwards trend of the errors. For about $t < 28$ s the LRSIF 2/2 solution is worse than the mixed order solution of LRSIF 1/2. Looking closely, the large error of LRSIF 2/2 starts to become visible for $K_{1,77}$ around $t = 0$ s.

The rank of the solutions X largely depends on the methods used, cf. Figure 7.8. The parareal scheme LRSIF 1/1 yields about the same ranks as the sequential LRSIF 1. Interestingly, the ranks of LRSIF 1/2 are not much larger, while showing the same plateau-effect. This causes the runtimes $t_F(n, k_n)$ and $t_G(n, k_n)$ to not deviate too much for different n . As can be seen in Figure 7.9, all methods of order 1/1 and 1/2 reasonably fulfill the assumptions of the timeline model (7.2) stated in Subsection 7.2.2, such that their timelines are close to the schematic in Figure 7.3. This can be confirmed by the small error in \hat{t}_{par} in Table 7.2. While for the dense methods this is to be expected, it allows some observations to be made for the low-rank methods:

Figure 7.7: Several parareal schemes (Rosenbrock methods of given coarse/fine order) applied to the problem of Example 2.1, running on $N = 450$ cores and computing up to $K = 10$ refinements. Each scheme performs one coarse step ($\tau = 100$ ms) and 100 fine steps ($\tau = 1$ ms) per stage. Top: trajectory of $K_{1,77}$ (same as Lang et al. [16, Fig. 1]), bottom: relative error (7.8) compared to reference solution (dense parareal scheme of order 4/4). Left: global time span [0s, 45s], right: zoom to [43.2s, 45s] (highlighted on the left).

- (i) Ros(1) is barely affected by the larger rank, which causes LRSIF 1/1 and LRSIF 1/2 to have about the same ramp-up delay. This delay, however, is about 0.2 s larger than the overhead for the dense algorithms.
- (ii) Due to its two stages, Ros(2) is more affected by the growing rank. Therefore, for LRSIF 1/2 the runtime $t_F(n, k)$ is monotonic in n . Yet, it is nearly constant in k , which causes the timeline diagram of LRSIF 2/2 to be narrow for early stages $n \leq 100$, and wider for later stages $n \geq 300$, without a noticeable gap between the refinements k .

The second effect is visible for LRSIF 1/1 as well, but not to that extent.

The rank of the solution X obtained from the parareal scheme LRSIF 2/2, however, is even larger than the rank produced by the sequential LRSIF 2, while showing the same growth behavior (for decreasing t), cf. Figure 7.8. As can be seen in Figure 7.9, neither of the methods of order 2/2 has a timeline diagram explained by the runtime model (7.2) or Figure 6.3, which is for the following reasons:

- (iii) For LRSIF 2/2 both runtimes $t_G(n, k)$ and $t_F(n, k)$ are monotonic in both n (due to the growing rank) and k , while also having a big deviation from their median. The monotonicity in k causes its timeline diagram to fan out, while the monotonicity in n causes each “feathers” k of the timeline diagram to be bent backwards. The resulting gaps between successive refinements k on the final stage $n = N$ are not considered by the schematic timeline, cf. Figure 7.3. Furthermore, the median over all $t_G(\cdot, \cdot)$ is much larger than, and therefore not a representative for $t_G(\cdot, 0)$, which determines the slope of the $k = 0$ face of the timeline. This causes the estimated ramp-up delay $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$ to become negative. Both effects, the gaps on stage $n = N$ as well as $t_{\text{ramp-up}} < 0$, attribute to the runtime model (7.2) greatly under-estimating the actual runtime, $\hat{t}_{\text{par}} < t_{\text{par}}$, as seen by the large error in Table 7.2.
- (iv) Dense 2/2 does not fulfill the assumption that all stages n compute the same number of refinements, i.e. k_n is not constant. Due to early convergence, cf. Subsection 7.2.4, the last stage $n = N$ for example computes fewer refinements, $k_N = 7 < 10 = K$. This causes the runtime model (7.2) to greatly over-estimate the actual runtime, $\hat{t}_{\text{par}} > t_{\text{par}}$, as seen by the large error in Table 7.2.

The timeline diagram of the Dense 4/4 reference solution is shown in Figure 7.2, which also does not fulfill all the assumptions of the runtime model (7.2) due to early convergence.

7.3.3 Runtime and Storage Size

Refer to Table 7.4 for the runtime and storage size of all resulting data sets. Note that the ratios of the sizes of the data sets resulting from sequential order 1 and parareal order 1/1 solvers fit well to the estimated 1/3 of Example 3.2. The other ratios are skewed by the rank problem of LRSIF Ros(2).

Figure 7.8: Numerical rank of low-rank parareal solutions to the Rail problem, cf. Lang [15, Figure 6.6b]. Only values at parareal interfaces t_n are shown, which coincide with the time steps of the sequential solutions. The numerical ranks of the sequential solutions, cf. Figure 7.4, are shown in the background.

Figure 7.9: Timeline diagrams for the parareal method applied to the Rail problem [22]. The schemes of coarse/fine order are as described in Figure 7.7.

Solver	k_N	$t_{\text{warm-up}}$	$t_{\text{ramp-up}}$	t_G	t_F	t_{par}	\hat{t}_{par}	$\left \frac{\hat{t}_{\text{par}} - t_{\text{par}}}{t_{\text{par}}} \right $
LRSIF 1/1	10	18.13	1.98	0.48	9.85	1243.84	1239.17	0.004
LRSIF 1/2	10	18.34	2.04	0.54	32.58	1659.48	1543.52	0.070
LRSIF 2/2	10	21.73	-1.63	5.06	30.97	4417.83	1959.42	0.556
Dense 1/1	10	19.76	1.74	1.86	178.99	3627.30	3627.17	<0.001
Dense 1/2	10	19.55	1.72	1.84	209.08	3956.86	3942.62	0.004
Dense 2/2	7	28.62	1.77	2.17	209.66	3602.36	4126.74	0.146
Dense 4/4	4	28.81	1.69	2.75	268.65	3381.88	5009.13	0.481

Table 7.2: Timeline measurements for parareal algorithm, $N = 450$, $K = 10$. All measurements and estimates are as in Table 7.1. The first column denotes the parareal scheme (coarse/fine order). Refer to Figures 7.9 and 7.2 for the corresponding timelines.

Solver	t_{par}	\hat{t}_{seq}	$\frac{\hat{t}_{\text{seq}}}{t_{\text{par}}}$	$\frac{\hat{t}_{\text{seq}}}{N \cdot t_{\text{par}}}$
LRSIF 1/1	1243.84	4313.10	3.47	0.008
LRSIF 1/2	1659.48	14054.91	8.47	0.019
LRSIF 2/2	4417.83	24565.04	5.56	0.012
Dense 1/1	3627.30	75037.71	20.69	0.046
Dense 1/2	3956.86	84595.61	21.38	0.048
Dense 2/2	3602.36	89274.94	24.78	0.055
Dense 4/4	3381.88	115091.06	34.03	0.076

Table 7.3: Speed-up and parallel efficiency of parareal algorithm, $N = 450$, $K = 10$. This table complements Table 7.2. The sequential runtime \hat{t}_{seq} is estimated according to Equation (7.6). The parallel efficiency is evaluated for N processors.

Solver	Order	Resolution [ms]	Runtime [s]		Size [GiB]	
			Dense	LRSIF	Dense	LRSIF
Sequential	1	100	217	599	0.472	0.165
Sequential	2	100	602	708	0.472	0.231
Parareal	1/1	1	4724	2366	47.047	15.971
Parareal	1/2	1	5057	2775	47.047	19.084
Parareal	2/2	1	4730	5519	47.047	35.161
Sequential	4	50	1785	–	0.942	–
Parareal	4/4	1	4512	–	47.047	–

Table 7.4: Overall runtime (as reported by Slurm) including time to write results to disk, and storage requirements of solutions to the Rail benchmark [22]. The resolution is the step size τ of the (fine) solver. The storage size includes both X and K trajectories, storing only K would result in substantially smaller files.

Conclusion

This thesis has given a brief overview of the DRE arising in optimal control in Chapter 2, and how to handle large-scale problems in general in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 has shown that applying the classical Rosenbrock method to the matrix-valued DRE results in the stage equations being ALEs having absolute terms in LRSIF. When solving these equations with the ADI method, the solution's low-rank structure causes the ADI sub-steps to operate on different low-rank factors. Due to the symmetry of the solution, and the particular choice of ADI parameters, these low-rank factors remain identical for every ADI iteration. Therefore, effectively only one of two ADI sub-steps has to be performed every iteration. It was further shown how the general structure of the ADI allows to efficiently iterate the low-rank residual alongside the solution, how to evaluate its norm without assembling the full residual matrix, and how to handle complex parameters using real arithmetic for the iterates. Lastly, Chapter 5 described how to choose ADI parameters based on quantities computed during the ADI iteration, i.e. independent from user input. An open research question is to explain the performance of these self-generating ADI shifts.

Chapter 6 and parts of Chapter 7 addressed the parareal method. It was shown how to apply the method to LRSIFs. When using the parareal method from a JIT compiled language like Julia, it is crucial that the coarse solver is already compiled before the parareal iteration starts. Otherwise, the overhead of compilation scales with the number of parareal stages N , rendering the method infeasible for practical use. Still, there is another linear overhead of about $t_{\text{ramp-up}} \approx 1.8\text{s}$ per stage, caused by the compilation of communication code. Overall, the efficiency is very low: less than 2% for the low-rank algorithms and 4.6% to 7.6% for the dense algorithms. Yet, the speed-up is very noticeable: e.g. more than 20 for the dense order 1/1 scheme, or 34 for the most expensive dense algorithm, cf. Table 7.3. For the low-rank algorithms, the speed-up is much lower, i.e. only about 3.5 for the LRSIF order 1/1 scheme. These metrics would be larger for finer temporal resolutions, a lower ramp-up delay $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$, or more advanced scheduling strategies. The latter would especially benefit the low-rank algorithms, and thereby could be another starting point for further research.

Numerically, the LRSIF version of Ros(1) performed just like its dense counterpart. The problem with the LRSIF version of Ros(2) as noted by Lang et al. [15, 16] has been reproduced in Julia. The cause of that problem needs further investigation. It is especially severe in a parareal context, which makes the comparison of runtime and derived metrics involving this method basically pointless. However, investigation is difficult as the level of introspection currently possible using `DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl`

is quite poor: it does not track the actual rank of the ALE right-hand sides, nor the number of ADI iterations or number of LRSIF compressions performed. Furthermore, the thresholds when to perform a LRSIF compression are not configurable yet, which would be necessary to apply the algorithms to large-scale problems.

Julia allows for user-friendly abstractions while still providing good performance. In particular, dynamic dispatch and extendable standard operators like (+) are very useful. It was mostly fun to work with, but could be improved in the following aspects. First, the runtime is too forgiving when errors occur, especially in a distributed environment. There is no simple way to make it more strict, e.g. to crash all worker processes on a single unhandled error. Second, the thread-safety of the standard library could be improved. This would allow `ParaReal.jl` to perform communication asynchronously. Third, Julia determines a suitable text representation of an object (e.g. `display()`) based on the number of terminal rows available. This applies to errors as well, causing e.g. grouped errors due to a parareal pipeline failure to only print the first error, which may not be the root cause of the problem. Subsequent errors are lost in an ellipsis (“... and 41 more exceptions”). In a truly headless setting, e.g. inside a job executed by a job scheduling system like Slurm,³⁴ all errors should be printed by default (or “... and 41 identical exceptions more”). Having these issues in mind, and considering that Julia is still a very young language compared to the ones dominant in high-performance computing, Julia certainly is an option worth considering for future projects in science and engineering.

³⁴<https://slurm.schedmd.com/overview.html>

APPENDIX A

ADI Reordering Following Li and White

Li and White [17] propose a reordering of the terms to simplify computations. The exact motivation will become apparent when applying the ADI method to an ALE. For an initial value of $x^0 = 0$, the ADI reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x^{k+1} &= G_k x^k + B_k b \\
 &= G_k G_{k-1} x^{k-1} + (G_k B_{k-1} + B_k) b \\
 &= G_k G_{k-1} (G_{k-2} x^{k-2} + B_{k-2} b) + (G_k B_{k-1} + B_k) b \\
 &= G_k \cdots G_{k-2} x^{k-2} + (G_k G_{k-1} B_{k-2} + G_k B_{k-1} + B_k) b \\
 &\quad \vdots \\
 &= \underbrace{G_k \cdots G_0}_{0} x^0 + (G_k \cdots G_1 B_0 + \dots + G_k B_{k-1} + B_k) b
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 5.1 allows to introduce a permutation σ of $\{0, \dots, k\}$. Thus:

$$= (G_{\sigma(k)} \cdots G_{\sigma(1)} B_{\sigma(0)} + \dots + G_{\sigma(k)} B_{\sigma(k-1)} + B_{\sigma(k)}) b$$

Choosing $\sigma = \sigma_k : i \mapsto k - i$, and exploiting that $G_* B_* = B_* G_*$ commute, yields:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (G_0 \cdots G_{k-1} B_k + \dots + G_0 B_1 + B_0) b \\
 &= (B_k G_{k-1} \cdots G_0 + \dots + B_1 G_0 + B_0) b
 \end{aligned}$$

Further utilizing $G_k := M_k^{-1} N_k = N_k M_k^{-1}$ and $B_k := M_k^{-1}$ leads to:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (M_k^{-1} (N_{k-1} M_{k-1}^{-1}) \cdots (N_0 M_0^{-1}) + \dots + M_1^{-1} (N_0 M_0^{-1}) + M_0^{-1}) b \\
 &= ((M_k^{-1} N_{k-1}) \cdots (M_1^{-1} N_0) M_0^{-1} + \dots + (M_1^{-1} N_0) M_0^{-1} + M_0^{-1}) b \\
 &= \underbrace{(M_k^{-1} N_{k-1}) \cdots (M_1^{-1} N_0) M_0^{-1}}_{v^k} b + \underbrace{(\dots + (M_1^{-1} N_0) M_0^{-1} + M_0^{-1})}_{x^k} b
 \end{aligned}$$

Regrouping reveals:

$$\begin{cases} x^{k+1} = x^k + v^k & x^0 = 0 \\ v^k = (M_k^{-1} N_{k-1}) v^{k-1} & v^0 = M_0^{-1} b \end{cases}$$

Kronecker Product and Vectorization

This chapter gives some more details on how to apply the concept's presented in Section 5.2 to ALEs, in particular how right-multiplication $X \mapsto XA^H$ can be described as a left-multiplication. The key ingredients for this are *vectorization* $\text{vec} : \mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{mn}$, e.g. for $X = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ with $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$

$$\text{vec}(X) := \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

and the *Kronecker product* $\otimes : \mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \times \mathbb{R}^{p \times q} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{mp \times nq}$,

$$A \otimes B := \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}B & \cdots & a_{1n}B \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1}B & \cdots & a_{mn}B \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Then, without a proof, the following holds:

Proposition B.1 (Kronecker Product). Let A, B, C be complex-valued matrices of compatible size. Then

$$\text{vec}(ABC) = (C^T \otimes A) \text{vec}(B).$$

△

In particular, in the context of Section 5.3 and the ALE (5.13), it is

$$\mathcal{L}_L \cong \text{vec}(X) \mapsto \text{vec}(AX) = (I \otimes A) \text{vec}(X) \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$\mathcal{L}_R \cong \text{vec}(X) \mapsto \text{vec}(XA^H) = (\bar{A} \otimes I) \text{vec}(X) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

such that the ALE

$$\mathcal{L}(X) = \mathcal{L}_L(X) + \mathcal{L}_R(X) = -W \quad (\text{B.5})$$

is equivalent to

$$(I \otimes A + \bar{A} \otimes I) \text{vec}(X) = -\text{vec}(W). \quad (\text{B.6})$$

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